

The Alan Turing Institute

Threat, Risk and Mitigation Taxonomy for Digital Identity Systems

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Executive Summary

Article 6 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that everyone has the right to a legal identity. Among many initiatives, digital identity (DID) aims to address this right. As such, DID systems are becoming an essential part of a growing modern society, serving as a foundational element for services in government, healthcare, finance, and other sectors that form the foundations of Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI). However, their increasing importance also makes them prime targets for exploitation by a diverse range of adversaries. This document aims to support stakeholders, including policymakers, security professionals, and system implementers, in managing these risks effectively. This report presents a threat taxonomy for DID systems, aimed at equipping stakeholders with a structured understanding of the principles, threats, risks, and response strategies, allowing a detailed approach to safeguard DIDs and broader DPIs. The details of the categories are as follows:

- *Threat Landscape*: The taxonomy identifies key aspects of the threat landscape, including motivations such as financial, political, and intelligence-driven goals; sources such as external, internal, and hybrid actors; and methods such as phishing, social engineering, and system exploitation. Threat vectors cover vulnerabilities in physical infrastructure, software, and communication systems.
- *Risk*: Risk assessment spans political, economic, societal, and technological domains, addressing impacts such as identity fraud, data theft, and reputation damage. These risks often create cascading effects in interconnected systems, highlighting the need for tailored responses based on the likelihood of the risk.
- *Response Strategies*: To counter these challenges, a multilayered defence approach is recommended, focusing on proactive monitoring, strong governance, and stakeholder collaboration. Response strategies are categorized into immediate, mid- and long-term actions, ensuring comprehensive mitigation of modern threats.

The structured approach provides a basis to enable proactive risk assessment and response planning, ensuring that DID systems remain secure against an increasingly sophisticated threat environment. It underscores the importance of continuous monitoring, the strengthening of security protocols, and collaborative cross-sector efforts to protect DID infrastructures against an increasingly complex threat environment.

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1 Background and Motivations

Digital Public Infrastructure (DPI) refers to the foundational systems and services that enable the management and authentication of digital identity. As a key component of DPI, Digital Identity (DID) systems are pivotal for modern society, underpinning secure and efficient interactions across both public and private sectors, enhancing operational efficiencies, while ensuring secure, reliable, and efficient access to essential public services. They enable access to critical services such as public administration, healthcare, banking, e-commerce, and online authentication, laying the foundations for digital transformation and becoming essential to the daily operations of individuals and organisations. Nevertheless, the growing dependence on these systems necessitates tackling the challenges arising from the quickly changing threat landscape of interconnected systems and guaranteeing their security against complex adversarial capabilities [1; 2; 3].

Key Motivations:

The motivations guiding this research reflect the priorities of governments, financial institutions, and other stakeholders invested in the security of DID infrastructures [4]:

- Government Motivations:
 - *National and Economic Security*: Protecting DID systems is critical to safeguarding national security and maintaining economic stability.
 - *Public Service Continuity*: Ensure uninterrupted access to essential public services, such as healthcare, welfare distribution, and administrative systems.
- Industry Motivations:
 - *Financial and Reputational Risk Management*: Financial institutions and private sector entities must minimize risks to prevent financial losses and protect the brand reputation.
 - *Regulatory Compliance*: Meeting stringent legal and regulatory requirements for data protection and cybersecurity.
- Motivations of this work:
 - *Proactive Threat Mitigation*: Establish a structured framework to identify, analyse, and counteract threats to DID systems before they materialise.
 - *Enhancing System Resilience*: Closing security gaps to ensure that DID infrastructures can withstand and recover from advanced and emerging cyber threats.

Services that benefit from the integration of digital ID include: 1) *Public Services*: Government platforms for identity verification and social welfare; 2) *Financial Services*: Online banking, digital wallets, and payment gateways; 3) *Sector based Applications*: E-Commerce, healthcare records, and identity-based access control systems.

The digital transformation of these services has enabled seamless authentication and secure transactions using digital ID; however, it also exposes systems to increased risks. Adversaries, ranging from individual hackers to state-sponsored actors, continue to exploit vulnerabilities, necessitating a proactive and structured response [5]. By framing the motivations and defining the scope of this work, research establishes the foundation for addressing the strategic needs of governments, financial institutions, and other critical stakeholders in securing DID systems.

Digital ID systems face an increased risk of exploitation with their growing importance. Because they hold sensitive personal and organisational data, these systems have become high-value targets for a diverse range of adversaries. Cybercriminals, nation-state actors, and insider threats are actively seeking to compromise them, motivated by financial gain, political influence, and intelligence gathering [6]. The complex and evolving nature of these threats presents significant challenges for security practitioners and decision makers, underscoring the need for a more structured and holistic approach to threat management [7].

Digital ID systems face a myriad of cyber threats, ranging from simple phishing attacks to complex multi-layered operations conducted by nation-state actors. Attackers exploit vulnerabilities in hardware, software,

and human behaviour to compromise these systems [2; 8]. The integration of advanced technologies such as biometric authentication, cloud-based identity solutions, and API-driven services has expanded the attack surface, making it harder to protect digital identities comprehensively. Threat actors leverage sophisticated tools and tactics to conduct identity theft, disrupt services, and manipulate data. The interconnectedness of systems means that a single breach can have a chain of effects that impact numerous sectors and services [9; 10].

Moreover, adversaries are becoming increasingly organised, utilising techniques that blur the lines between different types of attack. Phishing campaigns, for example, are often linked to broader efforts involving social engineering and system exploitation [11]. In some cases, nation-state actors employ cyber tools as part of strategic campaigns to weaken the infrastructure of rival countries, targeting national DID systems to destabilise societal operations [6]. The rapidly evolving threat landscape calls for proactive and structured measures to defend against these challenges.

This document formulates a taxonomy of known threats and risks to identity systems, along with response strategies, offering a comprehensive guide for executives and security professionals to apply at various management levels. The taxonomy breaks down the complex threat landscape into manageable components, focussing on key areas such as the motivations behind attacks, the various sources of threats, potential attack vectors, and strategic response mechanisms. In doing so, it provides a clear framework for understanding and minimising risks, allowing informed decision-making to protect these vital assets. As such, this taxonomy aims to support the development of defence strategies and governance structures that ensure the confidentiality, integrity, availability, and trustworthiness of DID infrastructures.

2 Introduction

A structured taxonomy is essential for effective threat, risk management and strategic planning. By categorising threats into clear and understandable segments, security professionals and decision makers can prioritise responses, allocate resources efficiently, and design comprehensive mitigation strategies. A detailed framework helps identify and analyse different types of threat, understand their potential impact, and develop response plans that align with organisational objectives. It also introduces a common language among stakeholders, ensuring cohesive efforts between departments and sectors to address shared risks [12; 13].

In addition, DID systems must adhere to foundational principles such as security, privacy, safety, resilience, reliability, robustness, and ethics. These principles, as discussed in Section 4, serve as key background considerations that inform the broader context in which threats, risks, and mitigation strategies are assessed. Ensuring compliance with established regulatory frameworks and best practices helps maintain the trustworthiness of digital identity systems [14].

This taxonomy, as illustrated in Figure 1, enables a comprehensive view of the threat landscape, breaking down complex scenarios into actionable insights [15]. For example, understanding the motivations behind various attacks helps predict adversarial behaviour and prevent potential breaches. Furthermore, a structured approach allows for continuous improvement, as it can be updated to reflect new threats, emerging technologies, and evolving adversary tactics. The benefits of implementing a comprehensive taxonomy are immense, enhancing situational awareness and strengthening the resilience of DID systems [12; 13].

The taxonomy, produced by The Alan Turing Institute team, is structured into three high-level classifications: Threat Landscape, Risk, and Response Strategies. Each of these classifications contains subcategories that provide a detailed framework to understand, assess, and respond to various threats to national identification systems.

1. *Threat Landscape*: Identifies and categorises the different vectors and motivations that pose risks to DID systems. This classification covers threat vectors, such as international threats, deception, and system exploitation, and the complexity of potential attack points, including software, hardware, data, and social engineering. The levels of preparedness and adversarial sources provide a granular view of the types and sophistication of threats, ranging from political motives to financial gain, highlighting the need for vigilance in anticipating and countering threats [16].
2. *Risk*: This section provides a structured assessment of the potential impacts associated with threats to national DID systems, including political, economic, social, technological, legal, and likelihood. By supporting the understanding of various types of impact, from diplomatic relations to civil unrest, and the associated costs, this classification enables decision-makers to prioritise risks effectively. The economic, social and legal impacts highlight the multifaceted nature of risk, highlighting the importance of comprehensive strategies to protect the resilience and integrity of national identification systems [17].
3. *Response Strategies*: Focusses on countermeasures and mitigation tactics that can be deployed at various stages to protect national identification systems. It includes immediate, mid-term, and long-term strategies that address the security lifecycle and stakeholder engagement. This section also delves into the governance and regulatory measures necessary to maintain system security and public trust. It considers both preventive actions and countermeasures to mitigate impacts, aligning response efforts with the urgency and scope of identified threats [18].

Figure 1: Threat Landscape, Risk and Mitigation Taxonomy

3 Methodology

The methodology for developing a comprehensive taxonomy for DID systems begins with an extensive review of the literature. This involves analysing academic research, industry standards, and regulatory frameworks, including ISO, NIST, and eIDAS, to understand the landscape of DID systems. Real-world incidents and reports of breaches are incorporated to highlight vulnerabilities and their exploits. In addition, insights are drawn from reports from the governmental and private sector to ensure that the taxonomy remains aligned with current and emerging threats.

The taxonomy is structured using a hierarchical framework to facilitate clarity and usability. It categorises the taxonomy into high-level classifications - Threat Landscape, Risk, and Response Strategies. These categories are further divided into subcategories and final categories, organised using a colour-coded system. High-level domains are represented by green boxes, mid-level themes by blue boxes, and detailed components by yellow, orange, and purple boxes. This structured approach ensures a logical flow from broad principles to specific actionable insights.

To map the threat landscape comprehensively, the taxonomy identifies adversarial sources, including internal, external, and hybrid threats, and analyses the motivations behind attacks, such as financial gain, political objectives, and experimentation. Attack vectors are categorised to encompass software vulnerabilities, social engineering, and hardware compromises, among others. In addition, the maturity levels of threats are assessed, ranging from existing and emerging threats to theoretical and obsolete ones.

The impact of risk is a critical component of the methodology, which evaluates the possible impacts of threats in the political, economic, social, technological and legal domains. This structured evaluation helps decision makers allocate resources effectively to mitigate the most pressing risks.

Mitigation strategies are designed to be actionable and bundled into immediate, mid- and long-term responses. These strategies include technical measures, such as zero-trust architecture and continuous vulnerability management, as well as governance protocols focussing on public trust, communication management, and cross-sector collaboration. This section of the taxonomy provides insightful guidelines to help ensure alignment with best practices and regulatory requirements, enhancing the resilience of DID systems.

Finally, the taxonomy is documented and presented in an accessible format, employing colour-coded hierarchies and visual aids for clarity. Comprehensive appendices are included to detail the selected threats, countermeasures, and their effectiveness. By integrating theoretical and practical insights, the methodology supports stakeholders in safeguarding DID systems through informed decision-making and proactive information on risk management.

4 Principles

The principles governing DID systems are foundational in ensuring their effective operation. These principles set the standard for designing, implementing and managing systems that are integral to public and private sector operations. Each principle, as explored in [19; 20], relevant to governing DID systems is described below:

4.1 Objectives

These objectives for establishing DID systems serve as fundamental principles guiding their design, implementation, and operation to ensure that they meet the set aim. The objectives outlined focus on key areas such as security, privacy, resiliency, reliability, robustness, and ethics, which collectively address the challenges and responsibilities inherent to the broader concepts of trustworthiness in the DID system and DPI in general. By adhering to these principles, the literature suggests that DID systems can develop, maintain, and maintain the trust and confidence of implementers and users, protect against emerging threats, and meet the expectations of stakeholders in a rapidly evolving digital landscape. Each objective emphasises a distinct, yet

interconnected aspect of system implementation, ensuring a holistic approach to safeguarding user interests and promoting inclusive and sustainable growth.

4.1.1 Security

Security is fundamental for DID systems, as it operates and handles sensitive personal and organisational data. This principle focusses on implementing comprehensive measures to prevent unauthorised access, data breaches, and cyber attacks by maintaining confidentiality, integrity, availability, authenticity, authorisation, and accountability. To ensure these requirements for a particular use-case, security may be ensured with various mechanisms such as encryption, authentication mechanisms, and continuous monitoring to protect data integrity and confidentiality. In addition, security frameworks must adapt to evolving threats, incorporating technologies like multi-factor authentication, secure software development practices, and comprehensive incident response plans.

4.1.2 Privacy

Privacy ensures that the collection, storage, and processing of personal information is in accordance with data protection laws and user expectations. It emphasises user consent, data minimisation, and anonymisation, where possible, with the notion of revealing minimal or only necessary data for any process. Privacy principles demand that systems are designed with privacy by default and by design, ensuring that personal data is not misused or exposed. Compliance with regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is essential for organisations using DID systems, as it ensures users have transparency and control over respective data.

4.1.3 Resilience

Resilience is the ability of DID systems to withstand and recover from adverse events, such as cyber attacks or system failures. This principle focusses on building systems that can continue operating under stress and recover quickly from interruptions. Resilient systems employ backup and recovery protocols, redundancy measures, and failover mechanisms to minimise downtime and data loss. Continuous testing and scenario planning are also critical to ensuring resilience in the face of evolving threats.

4.1.4 Reliability

Reliability ensures that DID systems perform consistently as expected, providing accurate and reliable identity verification and authentication services over time. This principle addresses system availability, uptime, and error rates. Reliable systems handle high volumes of requests without failure and provide consistent user experiences. Regular maintenance, system updates, and performance monitoring are necessary to ensure that reliability standards are met over time.

4.1.5 Robustness

Robustness refers to the strength of DID systems to handle a wide range of scenarios, including unexpected inputs or attacks to ensure the performance of the intended function. This principle emphasises designing systems that are resistant to errors, misuse, and malicious actions. A robust system anticipates potential vulnerabilities and includes protective measures to handle and overcome errors and exploits. For example, input validation, secure coding practices, and regular security assessments contribute to a system's robustness.

4.1.6 Ethics

Ethical considerations are vital in the development and deployment of DID systems, ensuring that their implementation respects fundamental human rights and promotes fairness, inclusivity, and accountability. Ethics guide the governance of these systems, emphasising responsible handling of personal data, preventing misuse, and ensuring equitable access for all individuals. An ethical system is required to address potential biases in design and operation, ensure transparency in decision-making processes, and promote accountability for all stakeholders involved. By embedding ethical principles into their foundation, DID systems can build trust, mitigate harm, and serve as enablers for social and economic progress while safeguarding individual dignity and autonomy.

4.2 Identity System Requirements

The effective management of DID systems requires structured processes to ensure security, privacy, and operational efficiency. These processes cover the full lifecycle of system development, implementation, and maintenance, providing a rigorous framework while adapting to emerging threats. According to the discussion in [21; 22], the following provides a comprehensive explanation of each process aligned with the taxonomy framework:

4.2.1 System Requirement Process

Identifies and documents the specific requirements for DID systems based on the local socio-technical context, including security, privacy (which encompasses both social and legal considerations), and performance metrics. It involves engaging with stakeholders to capture regulatory, organisational and user requirements. Clear documentation ensures alignment with goals and compliance with standards [4].

4.2.2 System Management Process

Focusses on overseeing the lifecycle management of the DID system, ensuring smooth transitions from one phase to another. This includes planning resource allocation, managing timelines, and proactively addressing management risks. Effective management ensures that the system evolves to meet user needs while maintaining reliability [23].

4.2.3 Architecture Engineering Process

Defines the architecture and design of the identity system, including its components, data interactions, and integration with internal and external systems. The emphasis is on scalability, modularity, and security, ensuring that the system can handle future growth and emerging threats [4].

4.2.4 Design and Implementation Process

Converts requirements into actionable designs and functional systems. This process includes selecting appropriate technologies, developing prototypes and conducting initial feasibility and iterative tests to refine and improve the performance of the system. Security considerations are integrated from the initial design stages [21].

4.2.5 Validation Process

Ensures that the system meets its defined requirements through comprehensive testing. Functional, security, and performance tests are performed to identify vulnerabilities and verify compliance with industry standards. User acceptance testing ensures that the system is in line with user expectations [4].

4.2.6 Delivery and Acceptance Process

Involves deploying the DID system in operational environments and ensuring that it meets the expectations of stakeholders. This phase includes final security audits, user onboarding, and documentation handover. It ensures that the system is ready to use in the real world with minimal disruption [23].

4.2.7 Verification Process

Verifies the alignment of the system with specified requirements and operational standards. This involves reviewing design documents, testing results, and compliance audits. Verification mitigates risks by identifying and addressing potential deficiencies before deployment [24].

4.2.8 Operation Process

Manages the daily functionality and performance of the DID system after deployment. Responsibilities include monitoring for anomalies, addressing user queries, and maintaining the integrity of identity data. Incident response plans are implemented to respond to threats promptly [23].

4.2.9 Maintenance Process

Ensures the system remains functional, secure, and up-to-date. Maintenance activities include regular patching, feature upgrades, and compliance reviews. Proactive monitoring and periodic audits are crucial to adapting to evolving threats and advances [24].

4.3 Standards and Methodologies

DID systems must adhere to standards and employ methodologies to ensure security, privacy, and reliability. These standards and methodologies provide a structured approach to system development, risk assessment, and compliance, ensuring that systems are resilient and well-governed. Here is a detailed description of key standards and methodologies used in managing DID systems.

4.3.1 Identity System Standards

Identity system standards are essential for ensuring secure, interoperable, and efficient identity management across organisations and platforms. They provide a consistent framework for authentication, authorisation, and access control, reducing security risks such as identity theft and unauthorised access. Standardised identity systems enhance user experience, streamline compliance with regulatory requirements, and facilitate seamless integration between different technologies and services. By adopting these standards, organisations can improve trust, security, and operational efficiency in digital identity management. Some of the key efforts are listed below.

4.3.1.1 UK Digital Identity and Attributes Trust Framework

As with other country trust frameworks these UK standards provide a comprehensive framework for the secure and efficient implementation of DID services in the UK. They emphasise user privacy, data protection, and interoperability between different systems. Compliance ensures that DID solutions meet national security requirements and are trusted by users and service providers [25].

4.3.1.2 NIST SP-800-63 DID Guidelines

These guidelines, established by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), define best practices for the management of DID. They focus on authentication, identity proofing, and federation, adopting a risk-based approach to ensure robust identity assurance. The guidelines are instrumental in mitigating the risks of unauthorised access while promoting strong security practices [24].

4.3.1.3 W3C Standards

Developed by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C), these standards address web-based identity technologies. They ensure interoperability and usability of DID systems in modern Web environments. Key specifications include decentralised identifiers (DIDs) and verifiable credentials, promoting secure and user-friendly DID solutions across platforms [26].

4.3.1.4 eIDAS Regulation

The Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services (eIDAS) regulation provides a unified framework for electronic identification in the European Union. It establishes legal requirements for the verification of DIDs between borders, enabling secure and seamless transactions. eIDAS promotes trust and standardisation in DID services within the EU [27].

4.3.1.5 ISO 24760: Framework for ID Management

This international standard outlines guidelines for managing digital identities securely. It focuses on protecting data integrity, ensuring privacy, and obtaining user consent. ISO 24760 provides organisations with a robust framework for developing secure identity management systems aligned with global security standards [28; 29].

4.3.2 Biometric System Standards

Biometric system standards are key to ensure accuracy, security, and interoperability of biometric technologies used for identity verification and authentication. They establish guidelines for data quality, privacy protection, and system performance, reducing the risks of fraud, false identifications, and security breaches. Standardised biometric systems enhance compatibility across different devices and platforms, enabling seamless integration and global adoption. Some of the key standards are listed below.

4.3.2.1 NIST Standards

The following are relevant NIST standards:

- *NIST-SP 500-290*: Defines biometric specifications for Personal Identity Verification (PIV), ensuring accuracy and interoperability in authentication.
- *ANSI/NIST-ITL 1-2011*: Specifies data formats for the interchange of fingerprint, facial, and other biometric information to enhance compatibility between systems.

4.3.2.2 ISO Standards

The following are relevant ISO standards:

- *ISO/IEC 19794*: Covers biometric data formats, including facial image data, vascular image data, iris image data, fingerprint minutiae, and finger vein data, ensuring global compatibility and efficiency.
- *ISO/IEC 30136*: Focusses on performance testing for biometric access control systems to validate reliability and accuracy.
- *ISO/IEC 19785*: Defines the Common Biometric Exchange Formats Framework, enabling seamless data exchange between systems.
- *ISO/IEC 24745*: Provides guidelines for the protection of biometric information to protect privacy and integrity of data.
- *ISO/IEC 30107*: Addresses Presentation Attack Detection (PAD) to prevent biometric spoofing and enhance security.

4.3.2.3 IEEE Standards

IEEE 2410-2021: Establishes the Biometric Open Protocol Standard (BOPS) for secure and interoperable biometric communications, fostering trust in biometric authentication systems.

4.3.3 Risk Assessment Methodologies

Risk assessment methodologies are essential for identifying, analysing, and mitigating potential threats that could impact an organisation's operations, assets, or personnel. They provide a structured approach to evaluating risks, ensuring informed decision-making, resource prioritisation, and compliance with regulatory requirements. By systematically assessing vulnerabilities and their potential consequences, organisations can proactively implement controls to minimise risks, enhance resilience, and improve overall security and safety. The most prominent tools are listed below.

4.3.3.1 TARA

Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) is a methodology focused on proactively identifying and mitigating cyber threats by analysing potential attack vectors and assessing associated risks. It prioritises threats based on their likelihood and impact, allowing organisations to allocate resources effectively to the most critical areas. TARA emphasises a risk-driven approach, integrating threat intelligence and vulnerability assessments to create comprehensive security strategies. This methodology is widely used to improve the security posture of DID systems by systematically addressing potential threats and implementing preventive measures [30].

4.3.3.2 STRIDE/DREAD

These are widely used threat modeling frameworks designed to systematically identify and evaluate potential security threats. STRIDE categorises threats into six classes: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service (DOS), and Elevation of Privilege, providing a structured approach for identifying vulnerabilities in systems. On the other hand, DREAD complements STRIDE by evaluating threats based on Damage potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected users, and Discoverability. Together, these frameworks help teams prioritise threats and allocate resources effectively [31; 16].

4.3.3.3 OCTAVE

The Operationally Critical Threat, Asset and Vulnerability Evaluation (OCTAVE) methodology is a risk-based approach that helps organisations assess and manage cybersecurity risks. It focuses on identifying and protecting critical assets, assessing vulnerabilities, and implementing targeted mitigation strategies. OCTAVE promotes collaboration among stakeholders and emphasises the importance of aligning risk management efforts with DID objectives. It is particularly useful in enabling DIDs to develop a comprehensive security strategy tailored to their specific context [32].

4.3.3.4 SABSA

The Sherwood Applied Business Security Architecture (SABSA) is a risk-driven methodology that integrates the enterprise security architecture into business processes. SABSA provides a framework for identifying and addressing risks at all levels of a DPI, from strategic planning to operational implementation. Its layered approach ensures that security initiatives align with DID business and operational goals and are adaptable to changing risks and requirements. By focusing on integration and business relevance, SABSA helps organisations build resilient and sustainable security architectures [33].

4.3.3.5 PASTA

The PASTA (Process for Attack Simulation and Threat Analysis) methodology is a risk-centric framework designed to align business objectives with security requirements. It follows a systemic process that includes defining objectives, analysing technical scope, identifying threats, and simulating attacks to assess risks. PASTA emphasizes the integration of the business context with technical threat modeling, enabling organisations to prioritise risks based on their impact and likelihood. This iterative approach helps stakeholders make informed decisions to protect critical assets and maintain system resilience.

4.3.3.6 FAIR

The Factor Analysis of Information Risk (FAIR) framework offers a structured methodology for understanding and quantifying information security risks. Unlike traditional qualitative methods, FAIR focuses on the financial impact of risks, allowing organisations to make informed, data-driven decisions. By quantifying risk in monetary terms, it provides a common language to communicate security priorities to business stakeholders and helps align risk management with organisational objectives [34].

4.3.3.7 CORAS

The CORAS methodology employs a model-based approach to risk assessment, using diagrams to visualise and analyse risks. This visual format improves communication among stakeholders, making it easier to identify, understand, and address security threats. CORAS supports iterative risk analysis and management processes, ensuring that risks are continually monitored and addressed as systems and threats evolve [35].

4.3.3.8 CRAMM

The CCTA Risk Analysis and Management Method (CRAMM) offers a comprehensive approach to risk assessment and mitigation. It involves three key phases: identifying assets, analysing threats and vulnerabilities, and selecting countermeasures. CRAMM is particularly useful for organisations seeking to establish a detailed understanding of their risk landscape and implement targeted security measures. Its systematic approach ensures that all critical aspects of risk management are addressed [36].

4.3.3.9 ISRAM

The Information Security Risk Analysis Method (ISRAM) focuses specifically on information security risks, offering a structured approach to evaluate the likelihood and impact of threats. It emphasises stakeholder participation, ensuring that risk assessments are tailored to organisational needs. ISRAM facilitates the prioritisation of risks and the selection of appropriate controls to mitigate them, making it an important consideration for DID systems [37].

4.3.3.10 ISO/IEC 27005

The ISO/IEC 27005 standard provides comprehensive guidelines for managing information security risks. It supports the implementation and operation of an Information Security Management System (ISMS), as outlined in ISO/IEC 27001. By offering a structured approach to identify, assess and mitigate risks, ISO / IEC 27005 helps organisations based on DPI maintain standardised security postures and align their practices with international standards [38].

4.3.3.11 IT-Grundschutz

Developed by the German Federal Information Security Office (BSI), IT-Grundschutz offers a systematic methodology to manage information security risks. It includes a catalogue of best practices and security controls, providing DPI based organisations with practical guidance for implementing comprehensive security measures. IT-Grundschutz is particularly popular in Europe and is recognised for its adaptability to diverse organisational contexts [39].

4.3.3.12 MAGERIT

The MAGERIT methodology, developed in Spain, is tailored for both public and private sector organisations. It emphasises the identification and evaluation of risks, focussing on their potential impact on critical assets. MAGERIT provides detailed guidance on the implementation of protective measures and is particularly suitable for operating in regulated environments or handling sensitive information [40].

4.3.3.13 MARION

The MARION methodology provides a structured framework for assessing and managing risks, with a particular focus on critical infrastructure protection. It emphasises systematic identification, evaluation, and mitigation of security threats, helping organisations build resilient systems that can withstand and recover from cyber threats [41].

4.3.3.14 MEHARI

The MEHARI method is a comprehensive risk assessment framework designed to assist organisations in identifying, analysing, and addressing risks within their information systems. Provides tools and methodologies for developing effective security strategies and aligning them with organisational goals. MEHARI is widely used in both the public and private sectors to improve security posture and ensure compliance with industry standards [42].

4.3.3.15 MIGRA

The MIGRA (Method for Information Security Risk Analysis) is a structured methodology designed to identify, evaluate, and manage risks related to information security. It focuses on assessing the likelihood and impact of potential threats while prioritising risk mitigation measures. MIGRA emphasises a systematic approach to understanding vulnerabilities, ensuring that security strategies are tailored to protect critical assets and align with organisational objectives.

4.3.3.16 SRMP

The Security Risk Management Process (SRMP) is a systematic approach to identifying, evaluating, and mitigating security risks to protect critical assets. It involves key steps such as risk identification, risk assessment, risk treatment, and continuous monitoring to ensure that risks are managed effectively. SRMP emphasises aligning security measures with organisational objectives and regulatory requirements, enabling a proactive and structured approach to minimising vulnerabilities and enhancing overall security posture.

4.4 Identity Assurance

Ensuring the security and integrity of DID systems requires assurance processes for both hardware and software components. ID Assurance encompasses strategies and practices to mitigate risks, validate system reliability, and maintain high standards throughout the lifecycle of the system. This section outlines the essential elements of ID Assurance, focusing on hardware and software security, implementation practices, secure development and integration, and quality assurance measures.

4.4.1 Hardware & Software Processes

The foundation of ID Assurance lies in ensuring that both hardware components and software are protected from vulnerabilities. These processes involve comprehensive risk management practices to secure the technology stack against cyber threats and unauthorised access.

4.4.1.1 Development Life Cycle

This process governs the end-to-end lifecycle of the hardware and software components, ensuring systematic planning, design, development, testing, deployment, and maintenance. Security is integrated into each stage to mitigate risks and adapt to evolving threats. Regular updates and audits are performed to maintain the integrity of the system throughout its operational life [43].

4.4.1.2 Individual Component Development Process

Focuses on the independent development of specific hardware or software components, such as biometric scanners, authentication modules, or cryptographic libraries. Each component is rigorously designed and tested to meet security, performance, and compliance standards. This process ensures that individual components can function securely and effectively when integrated into the larger system [44].

4.4.1.3 Collective Component Development Process

Involves the integration and co-development of hardware and software components, ensuring interoperability and system-level security. Collaborative development frameworks, such as DevSecOps, are used to align the security and functionality of interconnected components. Comprehensive system testing and validation are performed to ensure defence mechanisms against complex threats [43].

4.4.2 Implementation

Implementation refers to the integration of security measures into hardware and software components during the deployment phase. This process ensures that trust is embedded in every layer of the system rather than added as an afterthought.

4.4.2.1 Organisation & Responsibility

Clearly defines the roles and responsibilities within the organisation to ensure accountability in implementing security measures. This includes assigning tasks for monitoring, incident response, and compliance with security policies. Structured responsibility ensures effective collaboration between teams

4.4.2.2 Software Product Assurance Programme Management

Establishes a structured approach to ensure that software products meet quality and security standards throughout their lifecycle. This involves defining assurance objectives, implementing quality control practices, and tracking software performance after deployment [45].

4.4.2.3 Risk Management & Critical Item Control

Focusses on identifying and mitigating risks associated with critical hardware and software components. This includes risk assessments, threat modelling, and the implementation of controls to prevent unauthorised access or manipulation of key assets [43].

4.4.2.4 Supplier Selection & Control

Ensures that third-party suppliers adhere to security standards when providing components or services. This includes supplier audits, compliance checks, and the establishment of secure procurement practices to minimise supply chain risks [46].

4.4.2.5 Tools & Supporting Environment

Involves the deployment and management of tools that support the implementation of security measures. This includes development environments, configuration management tools, and monitoring systems to maintain security and operational efficiency [45].

4.4.2.6 Assessment & Improvement Process

Establishes a continuous evaluation mechanism to assess the effectiveness of implemented measures and identify areas for improvement. This involves regular security audits, system performance evaluations, and feedback mechanisms to ensure ongoing compliance and optimisation [43].

4.4.3 Product Quality Assurance

Product Quality Assurance focusses on maintaining high standards for system quality, performance, and security. Quality assurance processes ensure that the DID system meets all specified requirements and can withstand potential attacks [47]. To ensure that the DID system preserves its state, [45; 43; 44] suggests several quality assurance processes:

- *Quality Metrics:* Defining and measuring quality metrics, such as system uptime, response times, and the rate of security incidents. These metrics help assess the general health and security of the DID system and guide continuous improvement efforts.
- *Automated Testing:* Using automated testing tools to perform security, performance, and functionality tests. This ensures that the system operates reliably under various conditions and that the security controls are effective.
- *Manual Code Review:* Conducting thorough reviews of the source code to identify security flaws that automated tools may miss. Code reviews by security experts can uncover logic errors, potential vulnerabilities, and areas for optimisation.
- *Continuous Monitoring:* Implementing monitoring systems to detect and respond to security incidents in real time. This includes setting up alerts for unusual activities, monitoring system health, and analysing logs for signs of compromise.
- *User Acceptance Testing:* This involves user acceptance testing (UAT) to validate that the system meets their needs and expectations. This helps identify usability issues and ensures that security features do not hinder the user experience.

4.4.3.1 Quality Objectives and Metrication

This stage defines quality objectives for system performance, reliability, and security while establishing measurable criteria. Quality metrics such as system uptime, response times, and rate of security incidents are critical to evaluating the general health of the DID system and to guide continuous improvement efforts [45; 43; 44]. The metrics ensure that the system aligns with the intended goals and facilitates a transparent evaluation of its effectiveness.

4.4.3.2 Quality Requirements

Quality requirements specify the technical and functional standards that the system must meet to satisfy the expectations of the stakeholders. This includes compliance with security frameworks, compatibility with existing infrastructure, and adherence to industry best practices [45; 43; 44]. Rigorous validation processes ensure these requirements are met during development and deployment.

4.4.3.3 **Reuse**

Promoting scalability and modularity, this aspect focusses on designing reusable components and processes [45; 43; 44]. Reuse of well-tested, secure modules accelerates development, reduces errors, and ensures a consistent application of security measures throughout the system.

4.4.3.4 **Procurement**

The procurement phase emphasises the acquisition of components and services that align with predefined quality and security standards [45; 43; 44]. It involves a thorough vendor evaluation to ensure that purchased elements meet performance and security benchmarks.

4.4.3.5 **Firmware**

Software and firmwares serve as the foundational layer of the system's operation. It undergoes comprehensive quality assurance, including integrity checks, vulnerability assessments, and performance validation under variable conditions and states to ensure secure functionality [45; 43; 44].

5 Threat Landscape

The threats category consists of the following dimensions: vectors, adversarial sources, motivation, maturity level, complexity, and attack points — serve as the foundational pillars for understanding how threats manifest, their origins, and the underlying intent driving them.

5.1 Adversarial Sources

Threats to DID systems can be classified according to their origin, helping organisations identify where attacks are most likely to originate. Understanding these sources allows for more effective threat modelling and strategic mitigation efforts. Threat sources can be broadly classified into external and internal sources, each posing unique challenges and requiring tailored defensive measures.

- *Internal Threats*: This category includes issues such as disgruntled employees or contractors that present a significant risk. They may misuse their access to steal or compromise sensitive data [48; 49]. *Threats in focus*: An employee with elevated privileges downloads and sells user identity data to a criminal organisation. Mitigation strategies involve role-based access controls, regular audits, and employee monitoring systems to detect unusual behaviour (refer to Appendices A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No 7, 21) and Table A2 (S.No. 7, 21), for further details).
- *External Threats*: These originate outside the organisation and include nation states, cybercriminals, and hacktivist groups. Nation-state actors have also been known to target DID systems as part of larger cyber-espionage campaigns. *Threats in focus*: The 2020 SolarWinds attack exposed sensitive government data and underscored the vulnerabilities of interconnected digital infrastructures (refer to Appendices A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 15, 46) and Table A2 (S.No. 15, 46), for further details). Mitigation techniques include perimeter defences, threat intelligence sharing, and cross-border cooperation [50; 51; 52].

In addition, threats could also be coordinated attacks that combine internal and external elements. For example, an external actor may collaborate with an insider to bypass security measures. *Threats in focus*: A cybercriminal gains the cooperation of a system administrator to facilitate a breach. Addressing hybrid threats requires a holistic approach, combining external threat intelligence with internal monitoring [50]. Refer to Appendices A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No 2, 7, and 21) and Table A2 (S.No 2, 7, and 21), for further details.

5.1.1 Internal Threats

Internal threats (Figure 2) originate within the organisation, often from individuals who have legitimate access to sensitive systems and data. These threats are unique in their challenges because they exploit the trust and permissions granted to insiders.

Figure 2: Internal Sources

5.1.1.1 Insider threats

Employees, contractors or partners who intentionally misuse their access to harm the organisation. Motivations can include financial incentives, personal grievances, or the influence of external actors. Malicious insiders can steal data, sabotage systems, or share confidential information with competitors or adversaries [53; 54]. These threats can also come from well-meaning but careless individuals. *Threats in focus*: Employees who click on phishing links, use weak passwords, or do not follow security protocols. Negligent actions can inadvertently expose systems to external threats, making security awareness training critical to reducing these risks [55] (refer to Appendices A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 1,2,3,6, and 41) and Table A2 (S.No. 1, 2, 3, 6, and 41), for further details).

5.1.1.2 Misconfigurationism

Individuals with elevated access rights, such as system administrators or executives, pose a higher risk. If user accounts are compromised or misused, attackers can gain significant control over the organisation's identity systems. Monitoring and managing privileged access is essential to mitigate this threat [56]. Misconfiguration is a critical subset of internal threats within the broader spectrum of cybersecurity challenges. It refers to errors in the setup or management of systems, networks, or software that inadvertently expose vulnerabilities, making them susceptible to exploitation. Common examples include improper access controls, leaving sensitive data exposed, or using default credentials. Misconfigurations often arise from human error, lack of proper training, or oversight in adhering to security best practices. These issues can lead to significant breaches, and attackers can exploit these gaps to gain unauthorised access, disrupt operations, or exfiltrate data. Therefore, robust configuration management policies, regular audits, and automated tools to detect and mitigate configuration errors are essential for minimising this risk [57].

5.1.2 External Threats

External threats (Figure 3) are those that originate from actors outside the organisation. These adversaries often have specific motivations, whether financial, political, or ideological, and can range from lone attackers to highly organised groups with significant resources.

Figure 3: External Sources

5.1.2.1 **Cybercriminals**

These attackers seek financial gain by exploiting DID systems. They often employ tactics such as phishing, credential stuffing, or ransomware attacks to steal or hold sensitive identity data for ransom. Cybercriminal networks are known for their agility, constantly adapting their methods to bypass security measures [58].

5.1.2.2 **Hacktivists**

These are individuals or groups motivated by political or ideological causes. They target DID systems to promote their agenda, disrupt operations, or draw attention to specific issues. Hacktivist attacks can involve data leaks, website defacements, or distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks designed to make a statement or disrupt services [59].

5.1.2.3 **Nation-State Actors**

Governments or state-sponsored groups engage in cyber activities aimed at gaining intelligence, undermining the stability of rival nations, or disrupting critical infrastructure. These actors have significant resources and often use advanced persistent threats (APTs) to remain undetected for long periods. Examples include infiltrating government ID databases for espionage launching attacks to manipulate or sabotage national identity services [60; 61].

5.1.2.4 **Corporate Espionage**

Competitors may engage in espionage to gain a strategic advantage. This could involve the theft of proprietary algorithms used in DID verification or attempts to damage a competitor's reputation by compromising their security [53; 54].

5.1.2.5 **Supply Chain Attacks**

These occur when attackers infiltrate a trusted third-party vendor or service provider to gain access to the target organisation's systems. DID providers must be vigilant about the security practices of their partners, as a compromised supplier can create a gateway for attackers [62].

5.1.2.6 **Vendor Mismanagement**

Inadequate management of vendors and service providers introduces vulnerabilities that attackers can exploit.

Poorly enforced service level agreements (SLAs), insufficient audits, or lack of security protocols can allow attackers to leverage weaknesses in vendor systems to compromise the organisation's DID infrastructure [5].

5.1.2.7 Data Supply Chain

The data supply chain, which encompasses the flow of identity information from collection to storage and processing, is another area that is prone to attacks. Threat actors may intercept, manipulate, or steal sensitive data at various points, particularly if the data is transmitted insecurely or stored without adequate protections. Ensuring data integrity across the supply chain is critical [63].

5.1.2.8 Third-Party Software and Hardware Management

DID systems often rely on third-party software and hardware components, which can be compromised or manipulated to facilitate attacks. Vulnerabilities in software libraries, firmware, or hardware modules used in identity systems can create exploitable entry points. Comprehensive vulnerability assessments and regular patch management are essential to address these risks.

A combination of both internal and external elements forms hybrid sources, making them particularly challenging to defend against. These threats often involve coordinated attacks where external adversaries exploit internal actors to gain access or intelligence, or where internal actors facilitate external breaches

- *Coordinated Insider Collaboration:* In some cases, external attackers may recruit or coerce an insider to assist in their efforts. This collaboration can take many forms, such as providing login credentials, disabling security features, or creating backdoors for the attacker. Hybrid threats are especially dangerous because they combine the insider's knowledge of the organisation with the technical expertise of the external actor [64].
- *Supply Chain and Insider Combination:* Attackers may infiltrate a supply chain partner and then use that access to compromise an internal system, either directly or by enlisting the unintentional help of an insider. This form of attack requires comprehensive monitoring and secure supply chain practices to detect and mitigate [54].
- *Social Engineering and Phishing:* Hybrid attacks may also involve social engineering in which external adversaries manipulate insiders to take harmful actions. This could include convincing an employee to share sensitive information or unknowingly install malware on a secure network [65].

5.2 Motivation

The motivations driving threat actors to target DID systems vary significantly, and understanding these motivations is critical for developing effective defence strategies. Each motivation provides insight into why an adversary might attempt to compromise a system, the type of attack employed, and the resources they are willing to commit. Understanding the underlying motivations of the threat actors provides an essential context for anticipating and mitigating attacks. Motivation often dictates the nature and severity of the threat, as well as the tactics employed [66; 67; 68; 52]. The following subsections provide a detailed explanation of each motivation:

5.2.1 Political and Ideological Goals

Adversaries, particularly nation-state actors and hacktivists, may launch attacks to destabilise governments or promote specific ideologies. For instance, interference in national identity databases can disrupt electoral processes or damage public trust. Attacks motivated by political and ideological drivers often aim to disrupt systems, retaliate against perceived injustices, or promote specific agendas. The following are the political and ideologies (Figure 4):

Figure 4: Political and Ideological Goals

5.2.1.1 *Disruption and Destruction*

Threat actors seek to destabilise or incapacitate DID systems, causing widespread operational failures. These actions often aim to undermine public trust or disrupt government functions [66].

5.2.1.2 *Revenge/Retaliation*

Attacks motivated by grievances against governments, organisations, or individuals. These acts are often a response to perceived injustices and are intended to harm or discredit the targeted entity [69].

5.2.1.3 *Hacktivism*

Activists or politically motivated groups use cyberattacks as a form of protest. Activities may include website defacements, service disruptions, or leaks of sensitive information to promote a cause or draw attention to a problem [59].

5.2.2 Intelligence Gathering

Espionage activities by nation-state actors involve accessing sensitive data for strategic purposes. This includes collecting information about government officials, business leaders, or infrastructure. Intelligence-driven threats are typically highly complex and involve advanced persistent threats (APTs) that operate covertly for extended periods. Threats driven by intelligence gathering focus on acquiring sensitive information through various methods. These activities aim to gain strategic, economic, or political advantages. The key categories include (Figure 5):

Figure 5: Intelligence Gathering

5.2.2.1 *Surveillance and Monitoring*

Adversaries actively track and observe individuals or groups to gather insights into behaviours, networks, or operations. This often targets key personnel, political figures, or organisations for strategic purposes [5].

5.2.2.2 Data Harvesting

Focused on collecting large volumes of personal or organisational data. The information can be used to analyse trends, create profiles, or facilitate future attacks, such as identity theft or espionage operations. Gathering identity information can facilitate further espionage activities or enable the creation of false identities for covert operations. Adversaries may collect data to facilitate future attacks or infiltrate secure environments [58].

5.2.3 Financial Gain

Financial gain is a dominant motivation for many cybercriminals. DID systems are attractive targets because of the valuable personal and financial information they contain. These actors may engage in identity theft, fraudulent transactions, or ransomware attacks. The following are the financial goals (Figure 6):

Figure 6: Financial Gain

5.2.3.1 Theft - Funds

Cybercriminals are motivated by the potential for significant financial rewards. They may use stolen identities to perform fraudulent transactions, apply for loans, or access bank accounts [24].

5.2.3.2 Theft - Intellectual Property

Adversaries target the proprietary system and software architecture, operational procedures, and security designs to sell or misuse valuable information. These are further detailed as follows:

- *System and Software Architectures*: Adversaries seek to exploit weaknesses in proprietary systems to extract or manipulate data for financial gain [13].
- *Operational Procedures*: Vulnerabilities in operational workflows are targeted for extortion or disruption [5].
- *System Designs, Network, and Security Postures*: Security gaps in system designs and networks are exploited to access sensitive information or compromise operations [60].

5.2.3.3 Extortion

Sensitive data, such as personally identifiable information (PII) or system credentials, is held for ransom, with adversaries threatening to release or misuse the data unless demands are met [5].

5.2.3.4 Bug Bounties

Exploiting vulnerabilities to gain financial rewards through legitimate channels such as bug bounty programs or through unauthorised means, such as selling exploits of ID systems on the black market [70].

5.2.4 Personal Gain or Grievances

Insider threats are often motivated by personal grievances or the desire for revenge. Employees with access to sensitive information may intentionally leak or mislead data. Addressing this risk requires a strong focus on employee screening, behavioural monitoring, and a culture of security awareness. Motivations rooted in personal grievances or desires for individual gain can significantly threaten DID systems in DPI. The following are personal gain and grievances (Figure 7):

Figure 7: Personal Gain & Grievances

5.2.4.1 Blackmail

Insiders or external actors can exploit sensitive identity data to coerce individuals or organisations into meeting their demands. Such actions can alter the trust and functionality of public digital systems [52].

5.2.4.2 Reputation Manipulation

Adversaries may alter or falsify identity-related data to harm the reputation of individuals or institutions. This includes disseminating false information or manipulating records to discredit targets [5].

5.2.4.3 Reputation Damage

Malicious actors, including disgruntled employees or external attackers, can leak sensitive identity information or compromise systems to harm the reputation of public institutions, eroding trust in digital infrastructure [10].

5.2.5 Experimentation

Experimentation-driven threats to DID systems arise from actors motivated by curiosity, skill development, or personal interests. These activities, while not always malicious, can pose significant risks to the security and integrity of DPI. The following are the experimentation goals (Figure 8):

Figure 8: Experimentation

5.2.5.1 *Curiosity-driven Hacking*

Individuals may target DID systems to test their technical skills or explore vulnerabilities. Such activities, often conducted for personal learning, can inadvertently expose systems to exploitation [5].

5.2.5.2 *Research and Development*

Security researchers and ethical hackers can probe systems to identify weaknesses and propose improvements. Although their intentions may be constructive, uncoordinated or public disclosures can inadvertently attract malicious actors or introduce unforeseen risks [63].

5.2.5.3 *Hobbies*

Amateur hackers or enthusiasts may experiment with DID systems as a pastime, motivated by personal interests or a desire to understand how these systems work. Such actions can unintentionally compromise system security or privacy [71].

5.3 Vectors

This category includes tactics used by adversaries to gather, alter, or steal sensitive identity information, often with minimal technical complexity but significant consequences for trust and data integrity. Attack vectors, as discussed in [71], pose significant threats to the core functionalities of DID systems. These are:

- *Data Integrity*: Attacks such as database compromises and malware can corrupt or manipulate identity data, leading to inaccuracies and loss of trust in the system.
- *Confidentiality*: Techniques such as MITM attacks and data exfiltration compromise sensitive identity information, potentially violating privacy laws and regulations.
- *Availability*: Ransomware and service downtime attacks can make identity services unavailable, disrupting both public and private sector operations.
- *Authentication and Authorisation*: Deepfake technology and credential theft undermine the reliability of biometric and password-based authentication, necessitating rigorous, multi-factor solutions.
- *Scalability and Performance*: Cryptohacking and brute force attacks place additional load on systems, reducing performance and potentially causing outages.
- *Long-term Security*: Quantum computing poses a future threat to current encryption standards, requiring proactive investment in post-quantum cryptographic solutions.

5.3.1 Information Manipulation and Theft

Techniques (Figure 9) such as phishing and social engineering are used to trick people into revealing personal or system credentials. *Threats in focus:* Phishing campaigns targeting government employees to gain access to national ID databases. Identity theft can have long-term consequences that affect victims for years. Countermeasures include phishing awareness training and advanced email filtering technologies (*Refer to Appendix A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 6 and 41) and Table A2 (S.No. 6 and 41), for further details.*).

Figure 9: Information Manipulation and Theft

5.3.1.1 Collect and Analyse Information

Hackers seeking to test their skills or experiment with new methods may target DID systems. Although these attacks may not always have clear financial or political motives, they can still cause significant damage to the integrity of the system. Threat actors exploit DID systems to gather and analyse sensitive data using methods such as phishing, SIM swapping, social media takeovers, and database compromises [71]. Research also highlights the evolving methodologies in such attacks [72].

- *SIM Swapping:* Attackers manipulate telecom service providers to switch a victim’s phone number to a new SIM card. This allows interception of two-factor authentication (2FA) codes and SMS-based verifications. A successful SIM swap compromises authentication mechanisms reliant on SMS or phone-based verifications, jeopardizing access controls, and enabling account takeovers [73].
- *Phishing Attack:* Using deceptive emails or websites, attackers trick users into providing sensitive credentials such as usernames, passwords, or identification numbers. Stolen credentials can be lever-

aged to gain unauthorised access to DID systems, potentially compromising administrative accounts and enabling further system infiltration. Real-world incidents, such as ransomware campaigns initiated via phishing emails, demonstrate the pervasive nature of this threat. Preventative measures, including email filtering, user training, and continuous awareness programs, are critical to reducing susceptibility [74]. Refer to Appendix A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 6, 30, and 41) and Table A2 (S.No. 6, 30, and 41), for further details.

- *Social Media Account Takeover*: Attackers hijack social media accounts to impersonate users or collect personal information. Identity-based services integrated with social networks are at risk, as compromised accounts can be used to reset passwords or infiltrate connected services [75; 11].
- *ID Database Compromise*: Breaching identity record storage systems, such as government or corporate databases, exposes vast amounts of sensitive information. This often leads to data exfiltration, identity theft, and reputational damage, potentially undermining the security of the entire identity ecosystem [11].
- *Disclosure of ID Data*: Insider threats or inadequate security practices can lead to unintentional or intentional leakage of personal data. The resulting loss of data integrity and confidentiality impacts system trust, regulatory compliance, and the legitimacy of DID verification services [76; 77].
- *Surveillance*: Threat actors monitor user activities to collect identity-related data, compromising privacy and enabling targeted attacks. This undermines the trust framework of DID systems [78; 79].

5.3.1.2 **Fraud and Identity Theft**

Attackers exploit vulnerabilities to commit fraud and identity theft, using tactics such as SIM swaps, credential theft, and fake impersonations to gain unauthorised access and exploit systems.

- *SIM Swap Attack*: Similar to basic SIM swapping but often uses more complex techniques or insider help. Enables attackers to bypass multi-factor authentication and potentially lock out legitimate users. This can lead to account hijacking and disruption of services [73].
- *Insider SIM Swap*: Perpetrated with the help of telecom insiders who facilitate unauthorised SIM swaps. This adds complexity to security defences, as insider threats are difficult to detect and mitigate. Telecom partnerships must be secured through verification [73].
- *Social Engineering for SIM Swap*: Convincing telecom employees through manipulation or coercion to perform a SIM swap. The intrusion undermines identity verification processes, causing system administrators to reassess and strengthen verification methods [73].
- *Deepfake Audio Impersonation (Identity Spoofing)*: Using AI to mimic the voice of a target for authentication fraud. Threatens the integrity of voice-based authentication and highlights the need for multimodal biometric verification. DID systems relying solely on voice are especially vulnerable [79].
- *Privileged Account Compromise*: Gaining control of admin-level accounts to access or alter identity records. A compromised privileged account poses a high risk, potentially allowing attackers to modify, delete, or create identity records. This affects the integrity and availability of DID systems [11].
- *Credential Theft*: Using phishing, keyloggers, or malware to steal login credentials. Leads to unauthorised access to user or administrative accounts, creating opportunities for data manipulation or exfiltration. *Threats in focus*: It has been widely observed in real-world incidents such as the SolarWinds breach, where stolen credentials were leveraged to gain unauthorised access to critical systems (Refer to Appendix A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 1 and 3) and Table A2 (S.No. 1 and 3), for further details.). This threat is particularly significant due to its ability to bypass existing security measures and directly exploit system vulnerabilities. Effective countermeasures such as multi-factor authentication (MFA) are highly effective in mitigating credential theft. However, these require consistent implementation across systems and active user compliance to ensure their effectiveness [72].
- *Credential Stuffing*: Automated use of stolen credentials on multiple platforms, exploiting reused passwords. Stresses authentication mechanisms, leading to potential data breaches if password hygiene is

poor. *Threats in focus:* Credential stuffing attacks have been widely observed in large-scale breaches, where attackers leverage leaked credentials from one platform to compromise multiple accounts. This threat is particularly concerning as it exploits weak password hygiene and a lack of authentication safeguards. Effective mitigation strategies include rate limiting, MFA, and credential monitoring to detect reused or compromised credentials. However, their effectiveness depends on widespread adoption and user compliance [11]. Refer to Appendix A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 3) and Table A2 (S.No. 3), for further details.

- *Password Spraying:* Attempting common passwords across many accounts to avoid triggering account lockouts. Exploits weak password policies and can lead to widespread compromise. DID systems must enforce strong password requirements and implement anomaly detection [11].

5.3.2 System Exploitation

Adversaries exploit vulnerabilities in software and hardware to deploy malware, ransomware, or execute zero-day attacks as described in Figure 10. *Example:* A zero-day vulnerability in an identity management platform is exploited to exfiltrate sensitive user data. Mitigation includes patch management, vulnerability scanning, and incident response planning (see Appendix A, Table A1, S.No. 1 for further details).

Figure 10: System Exploitation

5.3.2.1 Inject Unexpected Items

Threat actors exploit vulnerabilities by introducing malicious items such as infostealer malware, ransomware, or Trojan attacks. These methods aim to disrupt operations, extract sensitive data, or lock systems for ransom, significantly impacting the integrity of DID systems.

- *Infostealer Malware (Ransomware):* Malware designed to steal data from identity systems or encrypt data for ransom. This can halt operations, cause significant data loss, and disrupt service availability [80]. Recovery often requires extensive forensic analysis and robust mitigation strategies [11].
- *Phishing-Driven Ransomware:* Delivering ransomware through phishing campaigns targeting identity management systems. These attacks disable access to critical identity services and compromise the long-term availability and integrity of data [75]. Securing backup systems and implementing phishing prevention measures are essential to mitigate this impact [81].

- *Malware and Trojan Attacks:* Malicious software masquerading as legitimate programs to provide attackers with backdoor access. This grants persistent access to the systems, enabling data theft or manipulation [82]. Endpoint protection, regular malware scans, and strict access controls are necessary to prevent such infiltrations [83].

5.3.2.2 **Employ Probabilistic Techniques**

Using probabilistic techniques, attackers target the digital infrastructure using strategies such as the 51% attack of ransomware on the cloud infrastructure [84]. These methods exploit statistical or computational weaknesses to manipulate systems and compromise DID security.

- *Cloud Infrastructure Ransomware (Scattered Splatter):* Distributed ransomware targeting cloud-based identity systems. This affects large-scale data storage and access management, disrupting operations for both service providers and end users. To mitigate this impact, cloud security measures must include robust data encryption and resilient recovery mechanisms [85; 11].
- *SIM Attack:* Probability-based attacks on SIM-related information to gain unauthorised access. These attacks can intercept communications and compromise identity systems. Mitigating this threat requires partnerships with telecom providers to implement enhanced security protocols and robust authentication measures [73; 86; 87].

5.3.2.3 **Subvert Access Control**

Attackers bypass access control mechanisms through tactics such as session hijacking, identity federation exploitation, and insider attacks. These methods undermine security frameworks, granting unauthorised access and exposing critical systems to exploitation.

- *Session Hijacking Attacks:* Taking over a user's session to act on their behalf. This threatens the integrity of user sessions, particularly if the DID system relies on session tokens. Mitigation strategies include employing strong encryption, implementing session timeouts, and monitoring anomalous session behaviour [82; 83].
- *Federated Identity Exploitation:* Attacking federated identity systems to gain broad access across multiple services. Such attacks can lead to a cascading compromise, simultaneously affecting numerous systems connected via identity federation. Secure identity federation standards and continuous monitoring are critical defences against these threats [72; 88].
- *Insider Attacks:* Threats originating within the organisation, often involving employees or contractors. These attacks are hard to detect and mitigate, especially when insiders have legitimate access. DID systems must incorporate behaviour monitoring, role-based access controls, and activity auditing to manage these risks effectively [49].

5.3.3 **Deception**

Deception-based attacks (Figure 11) trick or bypass DID system's security, often using advanced technologies such as AI and social engineering. Techniques such as impersonation, data spoofing, and deepfake technology are used to manipulate systems and people. *Example:* An attacker creates a fake DID to access restricted systems. Security measures such as biometric verification and digital watermarking can help counter these threats (see Appendix A, Table A1, S.No. 18 for further details).

5.3.3.1 **Engage in Deceptive Interaction**

Adversaries utilise sophisticated techniques such as fake phishing, biometric spoofing, or audio impersonation to manipulate user interactions and bypass authentication mechanisms.

Figure 11: Deception

- *Deepfake Attacks (Biometric Spoofing)*: Using realistic AI-generated visuals to fool facial recognition systems. This attack challenges the reliability of biometric systems, necessitating the use of anti-spoofing technology and MFA [89; 90].
- *Deepfake Audio Impersonation*: Mimicking voices for fraudulent purposes. For example, DeepFake audio spoofing represents a cutting-edge attack vector that exploits advanced deep learning technologies to mimic the voice of a targeted individual. This attack has severe implications for voice-based authentication systems, as it can facilitate fraud and cause significant reputational damage. Although deep-fake voice attacks are currently experimental, they are indicative of future threats that require proactive measures. Advanced detection technologies, MFA, and the integration of other biometric modalities are essential countermeasures to address this evolving threat [91]. This threat undermines voice authentication systems, making secure alternatives necessary, such as combining voice with facial or fingerprint verification [91; 92; 79].
- *Deepfake-driven Ransomware*: Using AI-generated deepfake content to deliver highly convincing phishing campaigns that result in ransomware attacks. These attacks exploit users' trust by presenting realistic visual or audio impersonations of trusted individuals or entities, coercing victims into executing malicious payloads. Countermeasures include the installation of advanced phishing detection systems, the integration of MFA, and regular training of users to recognise phishing attempts [90; 91].

5.3.3.2 Abuse Existing Functionality

Malicious actors exploit legitimate system features, such as session handling or API integrations, using techniques such as man-in-the-middle (MITM) or replay attacks to compromise data integrity and gain unauthorised access.

- *MITM Attack*: Intercepting and modifying communication between users and identity systems. This exposes data in transit, compromising the confidentiality and integrity of communications. Encryption (e.g. TLS) and secure key management are essential defences [83; 82].
- *Replay Attack*: Reusing captured authentication data to gain unauthorised access. This exploits systems without session expiration or encryption. DID systems should implement nonces and timestamp verification to counteract replay attacks [11; 72].
- *Brute Force Attack*: Systematically guessing passwords or keys. This puts a strain on the authentication systems, which can lead to unauthorised access. Rate-limiting and strong password requirements are needed to mitigate this threat [93].

5.3.3.3 **Manipulate Data Structures**

Threats targeting data structures involve altering or creating fake biometric identifiers (e.g., 3D printed fingerprints) or launching brute force and replay attacks to compromise authentication and authorisation processes [94; 95].

- *Fake Fingerprint Attack*: Using replicas of fingerprints to bypass scanners. This threat compromises biometric security, requiring advanced fingerprint recognition technology capable of detecting fakes [94].
- *Latent Fingerprint Attack*: Exploiting latent fingerprints left on surfaces. This undermines the reliability of fingerprint-based authentication. Combining fingerprints with other biometric factors can reduce risk [95].
- *Facial Print Attack*: Using 3D models to deceive facial recognition systems. This bypasses facial authentication, emphasising the need for liveness detection features to enhance system security [90].

5.3.3.4 **Manipulate System Resources**

Attackers misuse system resources through methods like cryptojacking, ransomware attacks, or quantum computing, causing service disruptions, unauthorised data extraction, or performance degradation.

- *Cryptohacking*: Using system resources for unauthorised crypto-mining. This reduces system performance and can expose vulnerabilities. Resource monitoring and anomaly detection are necessary to address this threat [11].
- *Quantum Computing Attack*: Using quantum algorithms to break encryption. This threatens existing cryptographic protections, highlighting the need to adopt post-quantum cryptography to mitigate this risk [84].
- *Brute Force Timing Attack*: Exploiting time-based vulnerabilities to gain information. This can reveal sensitive information through timing analysis. defence strategies include the use of constant-time algorithms to prevent such exploits [93].

5.3.3.5 **Manipulate Timing and State**

Adversaries exploit state or temporal vulnerabilities, such as exploiting 3D mask attacks or brute-force timing exploits, to bypass biometric or system authentication mechanisms and gain unauthorised access.

- *3D Mask Facial Attacks*: Using lifelike masks to deceive facial recognition systems. This bypasses facial biometrics, necessitating advanced anti-spoofing measures and multi-modal biometric systems to enhance security [96].

5.4 **Attack Points**

Attack points represent the specific areas or components of DID systems that adversaries can target. These points of vulnerability are critical to understand, as they provide insight into how attacks may be executed and where defences should be focused [71]. Here is a detailed breakdown of each attack point, tailored to the context of DID systems:

5.4.1 **Software**

The software infrastructure of DID systems (Figure 12) is a prime target for attackers looking to exploit vulnerabilities in code or system configuration.

Figure 12: Software

5.4.1.1 Identity Systems

Software that manages identity records and authentication processes can be targeted by malware, code injection, or exploits of unpatched vulnerabilities. Compromising these systems can allow attackers to alter or access sensitive identity data. These include:

- *Password Systems*: Password-based systems for identity verification are vulnerable to brute-force attacks, password spraying, and credential stuffing. These methods exploit weak or compromised passwords to gain unauthorised access, highlighting the need for strong password policies, account lockout mechanisms, and multifactor authentication (MFA) to improve security [93; 11].
- *Privileged Accounts*: High-level accounts with access to critical system components are targeted through privilege escalation, phishing, or insider threats. These attacks can result in severe breaches, such as unauthorised data modification, system manipulation, or complete shutdown, emphasising the importance of role-based access control and regular audits as necessary defences [88].
- *Cloud Identity Systems*: Cloud-hosted identity management services are vulnerable to attacks such as cloud misconfigurations, API abuse, and data exfiltration. These threats can expose identity data to unauthorised access or tampering, impacting data integrity and availability. Mitigation measures include secure API configurations, encryption, and continuous monitoring of cloud access [85].
- *Biometric Systems - Fingerprint, Facial, Iris, Voice Recognition*: Biometric systems for user authentication are vulnerable to attacks such as biometric spoofing, deepfake technology, and sensor tampering.

These compromises enabling unauthorised access or data theft undermine trust in user verification. Implementing multimodal biometric systems and detection of liveness is crucial to enhance security and prevent such attacks [94; 89].

- *Login Page:* Login pages are susceptible to attacks such as phishing and encrypting of credentials, allowing attackers to steal credentials or bypass authentication. Secure design practices, CAPTCHA, and anti-phishing mechanisms are critical defences [81].
- *Customer Support Systems:* Attackers often exploit customer support systems using social engineering tactics to manipulate support staff. They may pretend to be legitimate users and trick support agents into bypassing authentication steps, granting access to sensitive information, or making unauthorised changes to accounts. To reduce these risks, organisations should implement strict security protocols, such as multi-step identity verification, and train support teams to recognise and respond to suspicious behaviours. Regular updates to these protocols and ongoing staff training can help protect against these types of attacks [11].
- *Third-party Software:* Third-party tools integrated into identity systems may introduce vulnerabilities due to weak implementation or insufficient updates. Conducting regular vulnerability assessments and applying patches on time can reduce risk [97].

5.4.1.2 API Gateways

APIs that connect identity systems with external services are susceptible to attacks such as API key theft, injection attacks, or abuse of exposed endpoints [72]. Securing these APIs is essential to protect the flow of identity information.

- *Insecure API Endpoints:* APIs exposed to the Internet without proper security controls are vulnerable. The attack methods include exploiting vulnerabilities such as lack of authentication, SQL injection, or improper data validation [11]. The impact of API exploitation can lead to data breaches, unauthorised transactions, or service interruptions. Using secure API design principles and regular security testing is critical.
- *REST API Attacks:* Targeting vulnerabilities in REST APIs used for identity verification and management. Manipulating API requests to gain unauthorised access or expose sensitive data. Compromised APIs provide attackers with a direct route to manipulate identity data or disrupt services. Implementing authentication, rate limiting, and data encryption mitigates these threats [11].

5.4.1.3 Service Downtime

Attackers may launch DDoS attacks to overload identity service software, rendering it unavailable for legitimate use. Prolonged downtime can disrupt access to essential services, such as banking or government portals. Attack methods include transactions made using compromised or falsified identities. Affects system integrity and can lead to financial loss or reputational damage. Monitoring for unusual transaction patterns and the use of fraud detection systems are effective countermeasures [11].

- *Digital Tracking and Monitoring Tools:* Attackers exploit vulnerabilities in digital tracking and monitoring tools by disabling, overloading, or tampering with their data. These methods obscure system health metrics, delay threat detection, and hinder incident response [45]. The impact includes prolonged downtime, increased recovery costs, and reduced system visibility, leaving organisations vulnerable to undetected attacks. Countermeasures include ensuring redundancy in monitoring systems, the use of data integrity checks, the enforcement of strict access controls, and the isolation of monitoring tools from other systems to ensure continuous and secure operations [81; 71].
- *Cloud:* Cloud environments are targeted through DDoS attacks, resource hijacking, API exploitation, and privilege escalation, which disrupt ID services or deplete resources [45]. These attacks can lead to service outages, data breaches, and reputational harm. ID systems can mitigate these risks by deploying DDoS protection, conducting regular configuration audits, securing APIs with strong authentication and rate-limiting, and enforcing least privilege principles for cloud account access. Robust security practices ensure cloud services remain resilient against these threats [81; 71].

5.4.1.4 Fraudulent Transactions

Unauthorised or falsified transactions can lead to financial losses, compromised system integrity, and reputational damage [75]. Real-time monitoring and fraud detection tools help mitigate risks [52]. Attack methods include exploiting compromised or stolen credentials [45], leveraging social engineering to bypass authentication [71], using payment system vulnerabilities [81], or employing automated bots for transaction fraud [98]. This could lead to financial losses for users and organisations, damage to the integrity of the system through unauthorised access, and erosion of trust in the DID ecosystem. Mitigation measures include implementing real-time monitoring systems [45], anomaly detection [98], and robust fraud detection tools [71] to identify and prevent suspicious activities [75].

5.4.2 Hardware

Hardware-related (Figure 13) threats target the integrity of systems and devices, compromising critical systems and end-user equipment. Attacks on system integrity can result in loss of functionality, service downtime, or data corruption, while tampered hardware components or compromised end-user devices expose systems to further exploitation and unauthorised access. These vulnerabilities pose significant risks to the reliability and trustworthiness of DID systems. The following devices can be targeted:

Figure 13: Hardware

- *Biometric Devices*: Devices such as fingerprint scanners, facial recognition cameras, and iris scanners are integral to many DID systems. Attackers may attempt to tamper with or bypass these devices to gain unauthorised access or collect biometric data [94].
- *Tampered Hardware*: Physical tampering of hardware components, such as identity verification kiosks or servers, can lead to data breaches or manipulation of identity information. Attackers may implant hardware trojans or modify circuits to weaken the system [89].
- *Service Downtime*: Disabling or disrupting physical hardware components can lead to a DOS, affecting the availability of identity verification services. Attackers may target data centers or power supplies to achieve this [90].

5.4.2.1 System Integrity

Threats to the integrity of the system, such as service downtime, undermine the reliability and functionality of the critical operations in DPI, compromising the trust in the DID operations.

- *Loss of Integrity*: Hardware tampering or unauthorised modifications that compromise the integrity of system components of DID systems. Methods of attack include manipulation of hardware components,

firmware exploitation, or physical tampering of systems. This could lead to corrupted authentication data, invalid transactions, or unauthorised access, which poses long-term security risks. Regular hardware audits and tamper-proof mechanisms are vital for prevention [99; 100].

- *Service Downtime*: Attacks that lead to hardware failure or make devices temporarily unusable. Attack methods include DDoS attacks targeting hardware-dependent services, physical sabotage, or attacks on connected IoT devices. This could lead to disruption of the authentication and verification processes, potentially stopping access to essential services for legitimate users. Redundancy and secure backup systems are critical for mitigation [11; 76].

5.4.2.2 *Devices*

Compromised end-user devices or tampered hardware components can serve as entry points for attackers, enabling unauthorised access and exploitation of DID systems.

- *End-User Devices*: Includes smartphones, laptops, or biometric scanners used for identity verification. Attack Methods include physical theft, tampering, or malware installation. Attackers may compromise these devices to capture identity data, intercept communications, or manipulate authentication processes. If an end-user device is compromised, the attacker can intercept or manipulate identity-related transactions, leading to unauthorised access and breach of personal information. Security solutions must include device encryption, remote wipe capabilities, and secure boot mechanisms [73; 81].
- *Tampered Hardware Components*: Refers to malicious modifications of hardware used in DID verification. Attack methods include implanting malicious chips or tampering with biometric scanners to alter the behaviour of devices. This could lead to compromised hardware can result in false authentication outcomes, data manipulation, or backdoor access to sensitive identity information. Routine inspections, tamper-evident seals, and hardware attestation are required to mitigate these threats [100; 99].

5.4.3 *Data*

Attackers frequently target data (Figure 14) within DID systems, seeking to exfiltrate or manipulate them. Such attacks can have severe consequences, impacting the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of sensitive identity information [72; 84; 75]. Sensitive data transmitted between systems or devices is particularly vulnerable to interception [5; 7]. Attackers often employ MITM attacks or exploit weak encryption protocols to intercept or tamper with data during transit [83; 81]. This can lead to the exposure of authentication information or PII, compromising the confidentiality of DID systems and enabling further attacks [5]. Implementing encryption protocols and secure communication channels is critical to protecting data in transit [83; 69]. In addition, improperly protected credentials, such as passwords or tokens, are frequent targets for attackers within identity systems [89; 1]. Weak storage mechanisms, such as storing credentials in plaintext or using inadequate hashing techniques, allow attackers to steal and reuse these credentials for unauthorised access [5; 84]. Such breaches compromise the integrity and security of DID systems, enabling attackers to perform malicious actions. Employing secure storage techniques, such as salted hashing, is essential to mitigate these risks and enhance system security [84; 101].

5.4.3.1 *Data Exfiltration*

Data exfiltration involves the unauthorised extraction of sensitive information stored in DID systems.

- *Relational Databases*: Attackers exploit vulnerabilities in centralised identity repositories, such as SQL injection, malware, or insider threats, to access or steal structured data like PII, authentication tokens, or biometric records. This can result in identity theft, allowing attackers to impersonate individuals or conduct fraudulent and social engineering activities. Furthermore, privacy violations from these breaches erode trust in the system and expose organisations to regulatory fines and reputational damage [72].

Figure 14: Data

- *Blockchain Data Leaks*: Vulnerabilities in blockchain-based identity systems arise from improper key management, flaws in smart contracts, or insecure aggregation practices, allowing attackers to compromise sensitive identity records. The stolen data facilitate identity theft and pose significant privacy violations, erode trust and cause potential legal and reputational consequences [11; 74].
- *Cached Privacy-Related Information*: Temporary storage of sensitive information, such as session tokens or decrypted data, can be exploited through memory dumps or software vulnerabilities. This enables attackers to perform identity theft and compromises privacy, leading to loss of user confidence and regulatory penalties [102; 103].

5.4.3.2 Cryptographic Weaknesses

Cryptographic weaknesses can undermine the security of data stored or transmitted within DID systems, even when encryption is used.

- *Interception of Encrypted Communications*: Attackers use MITM attacks, side-channel techniques, or advanced computational resources to compromise encrypted data during transit. Weak or outdated encryption algorithms exacerbate this risk, leading to data exposure, where unauthorised access to encrypted information undermines the confidentiality of the system. This also introduces operational risks, as weak cryptographic systems jeopardise the integrity and reliability of DID solutions, potentially causing service interruptions [83; 11; 84].
- *Exploitation of Cryptographic Algorithms*: Poorly implemented cryptographic algorithms or insufficient key management can make encrypted data vulnerable to decryption. This results in data exposure, allowing unauthorised access to sensitive information, and operational risks, undermining the trustworthiness and functionality of DID systems [78; 74; 71].

5.4.4 Supply Chain

DID systems often rely on external vendors for components or services. A compromised third-party vendor can introduce vulnerabilities, such as malicious software updates or backdoors in hardware [5; 1]. In addition, many identity systems leverage cloud infrastructure, which can be a target for attacks if security configurations are weak [81; 61]. Attacks on cloud providers or misconfigurations can expose sensitive identity data [5; 7]. Furthermore, open-source libraries or third-party software used in identity systems can be exploited if they

contain vulnerabilities [88; 84]. Attackers may leverage these weaknesses to compromise the integrity of the identity system [72; 75]. Refer to Appendix A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 14, 15 and 46) and Table A2 (S.No. 14, 15 and 46), for further details.

Figure 15: Supply Chain

5.4.4.1 **Compromised Hardware Supply**

Hardware components used in DID systems are often sourced from multiple suppliers around the world. Attackers may compromise these components at any point in the supply chain (Figure 15), either by introducing malicious firmware, implanting hardware trojans, or altering the design of the components to create backdoors.

- *Malicious Firmware Injection:* Attackers inject malicious code into the firmware of devices such as biometric scanners or security modules, allowing unauthorised access or data exfiltration. This compromises the trustworthiness of the devices, undermining the integrity and reliability of the entire DID ecosystem. Furthermore, it facilitates data exfiltration, leaking sensitive identity information to attackers, and can enable system manipulation, allowing unauthorised actions and disruptions [11].
- *Hardware Trojans:* Tiny, hard-to-detect circuits embedded within chips allow attackers to bypass security mechanisms, steal data, or disrupt device functionality. This poses significant risks to device reliability, introduces opportunities for data exfiltration, and can cause operational disruption, affecting the availability of identity verification services [100; 74].
- *Design Alteration:* Tampering with the design or specifications of critical hardware components introduces hidden vulnerabilities. Such alterations compromise the trustworthiness of the device and can result in data exfiltration or system manipulation, allowing attackers to disrupt services or gain unauthorised access [71].
- *Intercepting Hardware During Transit:* Attackers intercept hardware shipments, modify components, and reintroduce them into the supply chain. This affects the trustworthiness of the devices, which can lead to data exfiltration and operational disruption, as compromised hardware becomes a vector for unauthorised access and service outages [100; 97].

5.4.4.2 **Third-Party Software and Vendor Access Risks**

DID systems often incorporate third-party software or rely on vendors for various services, such as cloud storage, authentication solutions, or software updates. These external dependencies create opportunities for attackers to exploit vulnerabilities in third-party software or gain access through compromised vendor networks.

- *Software Supply Chain Attacks:* Attackers compromise the development or distribution process of third-party software, injecting malicious code that gets distributed to all users of that software. This can lead to indirect data breaches, exposing sensitive identity information through vulnerabilities in third-party software, resulting in service disruption, degrading system performance, and affecting the availability of identity services [100; 97].

- *Vendor Network Breach*: Gaining unauthorised access to a vendor’s network and use it as a stepping stone to infiltrate DID systems. For example, attackers might exploit weak security in a vendor’s infrastructure to deliver malware to their clients. This escalates security risks by providing attackers with privileged access to identity systems and can cause service disruption or large-scale attacks [11; 76].
- *Backdoors in Third-Party Software*: Installing hidden backdoors that provide attackers with persistent, undetected access to DID systems. This compromises data integrity, allowing attackers to alter identity records or authentication processes, and contributes to increased security risks and indirect data breaches [100].
- *Dependency Hijacking*: Exploiting vulnerabilities in software dependencies or open source libraries used by DID systems. This enables indirect data breaches and poses risks to data integrity, allowing attackers to manipulate identity processes or records. Furthermore, it can cause service disruption and increased vulnerability to large-scale attacks [78; 11; 71].

An example includes attacks in which malicious code is injected into trusted vendor software updates. Robust vendor management practices, continuous security assessments, and securing third-party access are essential measures to mitigate the risks associated with supply chain attacks [11].

5.4.5 Communication

ID systems rely on secure communication channels (Figure 16) to transmit sensitive data during the onboarding, authentication, and verification processes. Attackers target these channels to intercept, manipulate, or disrupt communications, leading to compromised identity systems and unauthorised access. For example, MITM attacks target encrypted communications, allowing attackers to intercept sensitive data, commit fraud, and commit identity theft. These attacks pose a high risk because of their ability to compromise the confidentiality and integrity of communications. Although they require significant technical expertise, their impact can be devastating, particularly when encryption vulnerabilities are exploited. Effective mitigation strategies include the use of robust TLS encryption, VPNs, and secure implementation of communication protocols to minimise risks [74]. The primary areas of concern include the following.

Figure 16: Communication

5.4.5.1 Network Infrastructure

The underlying network that supports identity systems is vulnerable to various attacks.

- *Network-Based Attacks*: Network sniffing, protocol downgrades, and DNS hijacking redirect identity verification traffic to malicious servers. These attacks compromise the integrity of the data in transit, allowing attackers to intercept sensitive identity information or manipulate communications. Securing network infrastructure with advanced monitoring tools and encryption protocols is essential to mitigate these risks [83; 71; 11].

5.4.5.2 VPN

Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) and encrypted communication channels are critical to protecting identity system traffic.

- *VPN-Based Attacks:* VPN vulnerabilities, credential theft, or MITM attacks allow attackers to monitor or manipulate identity verification processes [81]. These attacks compromise sensitive communications and allow unauthorised access to DID systems [84]. Mitigation strategies include employing multi-factor authentication, regularly updating VPN software [83], and monitoring network traffic to detect anomalies [76].

5.4.5.3 Network Segmentation

Segmenting networks to limit access and isolate sensitive components enhances security.

- *Network Segmentation Attacks:* Bypassing segmentation controls or exploiting unsegmented networks allows attackers to move laterally within the network [11]. A poorly segmented network increases the attack surface, exposing identity systems to advanced threats [71]. Mitigation strategies include implementing micro-segmentation and conducting regular network audits to strengthen defences and reduce vulnerabilities [97; 100].

5.4.5.4 Firewall

Firewalls serve as a critical defence layer to control network traffic and prevent unauthorised access.

- *Firewall-Based Attacks:* Firewall evasion, misconfiguration exploitation, or DOS (DoS) attacks compromise network security [71]. These attacks expose sensitive data on the go, leading to unauthorised access or service interruptions [11]. Proper firewall configuration, regular updates, and continuous monitoring are essential to maintain security and mitigate such risks [103].

5.4.5.5 Client-Server Communication

The interaction between clients and servers during identity verification processes is a frequent target of attacks.

- *Communication Channel Attacks:* Intercepting or tampering with data exchanges through MITM attacks or exploiting unsecured communication channels [83]. These attacks expose sensitive identity information and disrupt authentication processes. Employing encryption protocols such as TLS (Transport Layer Security) and secure session management is crucial to safeguarding communications and maintaining the integrity of DID systems [78].

5.4.6 Social Engineering

Social engineering attacks, as shown in Figure 17, target the human element of security, manipulating people to reveal sensitive information or performing actions that compromise the security of DID systems. These attacks often exploit human trust, psychological manipulation, and technological vulnerabilities, making them highly effective even if they require minimal technical expertise. Social engineering attacks pose a critical risk because they exploit human behaviour rather than system vulnerabilities.

5.4.6.1 Phishing

Phishing involves deceptive messages, through email, text, or social media, that appear to come from legitimate sources, tricking users into revealing sensitive information such as login credentials or financial data. These attacks enable unauthorised access to user accounts, leading to identity theft or fraudulent activities. Stolen credentials can also result in data breaches, allowing attackers to infiltrate systems and exfiltrate sensitive identity data [81].

- *Email Phishing:* Fraudulent emails mimic official communications, causing victims to click malicious links or provide sensitive information [11].

Figure 17: Social Engineering

- *Social Media Links and Platforms*: Attackers exploit social media platforms to distribute phishing links and collect user information [75].

5.4.6.2 Impersonation Attacks

Impersonation attacks involve attackers using technology to mimic trusted individuals, creating a false sense of legitimacy to gain access to or extract sensitive information. These attacks allow attackers to bypass identity verification systems, such as voice authentication or liveness detection. In addition, they enable social engineering, where victims may unknowingly disclose security codes or other critical information.

- *Voice Call Spoofing*: AI-generated or manipulated voice calls mimic trusted individuals, persuading victims to share sensitive information [91; 92].
- *Voice-Based Authentication Manipulation*: Exploiting voice-based systems to bypass security measures by synthesising or mimicking a target's voice [89; 91; 96].

5.4.6.3 Telecom Exploitation

Telecom exploitation targets vulnerabilities in telecommunication systems, which undermine SMS-based authentication and voice verification processes. These attacks compromise authentication by allowing attackers to intercept SMS-based verification codes, granting unauthorised access to user accounts. Additionally, manipulation of voice verification through spoofed calls or synthesised voices can bypass voice authentication mechanisms, further exposing identity systems to security risks.

- *SIM Card Attacks*: SIM swapping tricks telecom providers into transferring the victim's phone number to a new SIM card, allowing the intercept of verification codes [73; 86].
- *Telecom Employee/Service Manipulation*: Social engineering of telecom staff to gain access to customer data or exploit telecom services for unauthorised actions [87; 11].
- *Telecom Customer Service Exploitation*: Manipulating customer service processes to reset accounts or retrieve sensitive information [73; 71].

5.4.7 Physical Security

Physical security measures (Figure 18) are a critical component of protecting DID systems. Although much attention is given to cyber threats, physical attacks on infrastructure and devices can be equally damaging.

These attacks can result in unauthorised access, data breaches, system manipulation, and service disruptions, making physical security an essential aspect of a comprehensive defence strategy.

Figure 18: Physical Security

5.4.7.1 Device Theft

Attackers often target end-user devices, such as laptops, smartphones, or tablets, that store or process DID data. These devices are particularly vulnerable due to their mobility and accessibility in public spaces, offices, or even secured environments [73]. Such attacks can expose sensitive identity information or allow unauthorised access to the systems [11]. Mitigation strategies include enforcing device encryption, multi-factor authentication, and device tracking [71; 100].

- *Opportunistic Theft*: Stealing unattended devices from public spaces, offices, or vehicles. This leads to data compromise by allowing attackers to access identity systems or compromise user accounts using unencrypted personal or authentication data [73; 71].
- *Targeted Theft*: Deliberately targeting high-value individuals, such as executives or administrators, who have access to sensitive systems. Such attacks can undermine data integrity as attackers manipulate stored data, introduce false records, or manipulate identity information [11; 78].
- *Break-Ins*: Gaining physical access to offices or homes to steal devices that contain valuable data. This enables access to authentication mechanisms, as attackers can exploit devices used for MFA (e.g. receiving OTP or using biometric authentication) to gain unauthorised entry into secure systems [100].
- *Coercion and Threats*: Forcing individuals to hand over devices through threats or physical coercion. This can result in privacy violations, with attackers accessing communication applications or identity management tools on stolen devices, causing widespread privacy breaches and unauthorised access to data [11; 73].

5.4.7.2 Unauthorised Facility Access

Attackers may attempt to gain unauthorised physical access to secure facilities, such as data centres, server rooms, or offices where DID infrastructure is housed. These facilities often contain critical servers, backup systems, or physical records that are vital to the operation and security of DID systems.

- *Tailgating and Piggybacking*: Following authorised personnel through secure doors without proper authentication. This method allows attackers to gain physical access to servers or storage devices, leading to data theft and significant privacy breaches [71].
- *Impersonation*: Pretending to be trusted individuals, such as maintenance workers or delivery personnel, to gain access. This enables attackers to alter systems by installing hardware-based malware, modifying network infrastructure, or compromising critical system components, thus undermining the integrity and security of the identity system [11].
- *Lock Picking and Bypassing Security Systems*: Using tools or techniques to bypass physical locks, access control systems, or security barriers. Such attacks facilitate unauthorised access, leading to data theft and potential sabotage of identity systems, including service disruptions [100].

- *Destruction of Security Measures*: Breaking down doors or disabling surveillance cameras to enter restricted areas undetected. This can cause direct physical damage to the equipment, leading to disruption, downtime, and impaired identity verification processes [78].

5.5 Threat Complexity

The complexity of threats to DID systems can vary significantly, depending on the sophistication of the techniques used and the resources required to execute them. Understanding the complexity of these threats helps to prioritise defence strategies and allocate resources effectively [104]. Here is a breakdown of the complexity levels, tuned to the context of DID systems [105]:

5.5.1 Low

- *Basic Phishing Attacks*: These are simple, often automated attacks that require little technical skill. Attackers use mass phishing campaigns to trick users into revealing their credentials [81]. Although these attacks are not technically complex, they can still be effective if users are not adequately trained in security awareness.
- *Brute Force Attacks*: Automated attempts to guess user credentials using common passwords or dictionary attacks fall under low complexity [84]. These attacks rely on the weakness of user passwords rather than exploiting system vulnerabilities.
- *Simple Social Engineering*: Convincing an individual to provide information or perform an action using basic psychological tactics, such as impersonating a co-worker, is another example of a low-complexity threat [83]. These attacks are often opportunistic and require minimal preparation.

5.5.2 Medium

- *MITM Attacks*: These attacks require moderate technical skills and knowledge of network protocols. An attacker intercepts communication between two parties to eavesdrop or alter data in transit. MITM attacks often target identity verification processes, especially those relying on unsecured or poorly configured communication channels [76].
- *SQL Injection*: Exploiting vulnerabilities in web applications to access or manipulate databases that store identity information [106]. This attack requires an understanding of how web applications interact with databases and can be used to extract sensitive identity records.
- *Credential Stuffing*: Using automated tools to test large volumes of stolen credentials against DID systems [37]. This type of attack is more sophisticated than brute force as it involves leveraging previously compromised username-password pairs and is often carried out using botnets to avoid detection.
- *Session Hijacking*: This involves stealing or intercepting a user's session token to gain unauthorised access to identity systems [91]. This attack requires moderate knowledge of how sessions are managed and how to manipulate them.

5.5.3 High

- *Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs)*: These are sophisticated long-term attacks, that are often carried out by actors in the nation-states or well-funded cybercriminal organisations [20]. APTs use a combination of methods, including spear phishing, malware, and zero-day exploits, to maintain prolonged access to the target's systems. They may specifically target the DID infrastructure for intelligence gathering or disruption.

- *Zero-Day Exploits*: Attacks that take advantage of vulnerabilities not yet known or patched by the software vendor [52]. These require advanced knowledge of the target system and the ability to develop or acquire specialised exploit code. Attackers using zero-day exploits are often highly skilled and well-resourced.
- *Deepfake Technology*: Using AI-generated media to impersonate people for identity fraud or bypass biometric verification systems [91]. This attack involves a deep understanding of machine learning and access to advanced technology to generate convincing fake audio or video.
- *Supply Chain Attacks*: Compromising a third-party vendor to infiltrate an organisation's identity systems [12]. This attack requires significant planning, understanding of the target's supply chain, and resources to execute effectively. Examples include introducing malicious code into software updates or tampering with hardware components before they are deployed.
- *SIM Swapping Attacks*: These attacks target the mobile network infrastructure to take over a victim's phone number and intercept two-factor authentication codes based on SMS [68]. They require social engineering to manipulate telecom employees and an understanding of telecom protocols.
- *Blockchain Exploitation*: For identity systems using blockchain technology attacks can involve exploiting vulnerabilities in smart contracts or attempting a 51% attack on the network [84]. This level of attack requires extensive knowledge of blockchain technology and significant computational resources.
- *Insider Threat Collaboration*: Coordinated efforts between external attackers and internal employees who have insider knowledge of the DID system [5]. This type of attack involves strategic planning and execution, which makes it very complex to detect and mitigate. For example, insider sabotage poses a serious threat to DPs by causing operational disruptions and financial losses. Unlike external threats, insider sabotage is particularly difficult to mitigate due to the inherent trust placed in insider roles. A prominent real-world example is the Tesla insider sabotage case, where an employee deliberately manipulated critical systems. This highlights the importance of strict access controls, continuous monitoring, and a robust security culture to detect and prevent such activities [78]. Refer to Appendices A and B, specifically Table A1 (S.No. 2,7 and 21) and Table A2 (S.No. 2,7 and 21), for further details.

5.6 Threat Maturity Level

Threat maturity levels refer to the various stages or readiness levels that organisations can utilise to assess and improve their defence mechanisms against threats to DID systems [104; 69]. The following are the details:

5.6.1 Existing Threats

This level refers to threats or vulnerabilities that have already manifested in real-world scenarios. Examples include actual cyberattacks on DID systems, such as breaches of national ID databases or exploitation of biometric systems [68]. Addressing real-life incidents requires immediate action, including incident response, root cause analysis, and implementation of corrective measures. The lessons learnt can help reinforce the overall security posture.

5.6.2 In-Development

This stage refers to threats that are actively being developed or refined by adversaries. For example, attackers might be working on new methods to bypass biometric authentication or exploit vulnerabilities in identity APIs [84]. Recognising and monitoring these threats allows organisations to proactively implement safeguards before such attacks become operational.

5.6.3 Theoretical

Describe threats that have not yet materialised but could pose a significant risk to DID systems in the future. These include hypothetical scenarios based on emerging trends, such as advancements in quantum computing that could compromise encryption [63] or evolving deep-fake technologies that may fool biometric systems. Focussing on these enables organisations to anticipate and prepare for future threats by investing in research and development, implementing forward-thinking security measures, and staying informed through proactive threat intelligence. For DID systems, this can involve exploring quantum-resistant cryptography or enhancing liveness detection mechanisms [63].

5.6.4 Emerging

Monitoring newly identified threats and attack methods that are currently being developed. For example, novel techniques for biometric spoofing [94], new malware targeting DID databases, or the latest phishing strategies that exploit multi-factor authentication [68]. This keeps DID systems up-to-date and resilient against the latest security challenges. Continuous monitoring of the threat landscape and rapid response mechanisms allow timely updates to security protocols, ensuring that systems can defend against modern attack techniques and emerging risks [69; 68].

5.6.5 Simulated

Conducting controlled simulations and exercises to test the resilience of DID systems against various attack vectors. This includes phishing simulation drills [84], penetration tests in biometric verification modules, or stress tests on API gateways that handle identity data [107]. This helps assess the effectiveness of specific defence and response protocols for DID infrastructures. By simulating breaches or identity fraud attempts, organisations can identify vulnerabilities, assess staff readiness, and improve security measures, such as user behaviour monitoring or advanced access controls [101; 107].

5.6.6 Historical

Drawing on past security incidents related to DID systems, such as major data breaches, cases of identity theft [108], or successful attacks on authentication mechanisms [106], allows preparation for future threats. The lessons learnt from these historical events guide the implementation of stronger security controls and policies. This ensures that the DID system's security posture evolves based on real-world experiences. By understanding how and why previous breaches occurred, organisations can refine data protection practices, improve identity verification processes, and establish better incident response plans [108; 106; 68].

5.6.7 Obsolete

This category refers to security processes, mechanisms, or controls that were once used to protect DID systems but have been rendered ineffective or replaced due to advances in security practices. Examples include deprecated encryption algorithms, outdated authentication protocols, and retired identity verification methods that have been replaced by more useful alternatives [109; 57]. Understanding these obsolete security measures is critical to ensure that identity systems do not rely on legacy protections that do not meet modern security standards. Documenting such measures serves as a reference for historical security evolution and informs the development of future-proof identity system architectures [109; 57].

6 Risk

Risk analysis involves assessing both the impact and the likelihood of potential threats, enabling organisations to prioritise and allocate resources effectively. The consequences of a successful attack can be extensive and affect the political, economic, social, technological, and legal domains [110]. This section covers the following:

- *Political Impact:* Attacks on national identity systems can undermine government stability and international relations.
- *Economic Impact:* Financial losses from data breaches can be severe and affect stock prices and investor confidence.
- *Social Impact:* Compromises in DID can erode public trust and have long-term implications for societal security.
- *Technological Impact:* Disruptions in identity systems can lead to widespread service outages and reputation damage to service providers.
- *Legal Impact:* Non-compliance with data protection regulations can result in hefty fines and legal consequences. Breaches involving sensitive personal information can trigger regulatory scrutiny and legal action.
- *Likelihood Evaluation:* Threats are classified according to their probability: critical, high, medium, or low. This classification helps organisations determine which threats to address first and how to allocate security resources efficiently.

6.1 Political Impact

The political impact of cyber threats to DID systems encompasses risks that affect governance, international relations, policy alignment, and societal stability. This component of the taxonomy highlights the socio-political dimensions of cyber risks, which can influence diplomatic ties, government relations, and public trust [110; 111]. Addressing these challenges requires careful consideration of ethical practices, transparent communication, and collaboration between stakeholders to prevent political instability and maintain trust in DID initiatives. In the following, the subcategories detail specific areas of political impact.

6.1.1 Diplomatic Relations

ID systems can influence international collaboration and agreements, with misuse or failure of them potentially causing tensions between countries [110]. For example, data breaches or unauthorised surveillance linked to identity systems can lead to diplomatic conflicts or mistrust among nations. To mitigate these risks, governments and organisations are obligated to establish international standards, promote transparency, and ensure accountability in the development and deployment of these systems. Strengthening diplomatic ties through cybersecurity agreements and cross-border collaborations also helps address potential conflicts [111].

6.1.2 Investor and Stakeholder Relations

Cyber threats to DID systems can undermine investor, partner, and other stakeholders confidence, directly influencing financial support and collaboration [110]. Security incidents, mismanagement, or policy misalignment can deter stakeholders from funding or supporting these systems. To maintain investor confidence, organisations must demonstrate security practices, ensure transparent governance, and provide clear communication on risk management and mitigation strategies [104].

6.1.3 State and National Government Relations

Tensions may arise between state and national authorities due to mismanagement or vulnerabilities in DID systems, particularly if they impact the alignment of policies or the delivery of services [111]. Such conflicts can undermine cooperative governance and hinder the implementation of national ID initiatives. Addressing this requires strengthening collaboration between various levels of government, ensuring alignment of objectives, and maintaining accountability in managing and securing DID systems.

6.1.4 Civil Unrest

Public opposition to ID initiatives can lead to societal disruptions, including protests, activism, or resistance movements [110]. Concerns related to privacy, discrimination, or exclusion from access to digital services often fuel dissatisfaction. These risks can destabilise social trust and hinder the adoption of identity systems. Proactively addressing these concerns through inclusive policymaking, public education, and transparent practices is essential to mitigate civil unrest and maintain social harmony [111].

6.2 Economical Impact

The economical impact of cyber threats to DID systems highlights the financial vulnerabilities and market-related consequences that arise from security incidents. This component of the taxonomy focusses on the direct and indirect economic repercussions of cyber threats, underlining the critical need for robust mitigation strategies. Addressing these risks is essential to ensure the financial stability of organisations and maintain investor confidence in DID systems [105].

6.2.1 Financial Impact

Cyber threats can cause significant direct financial losses through incidents such as fraud, identity theft, system downtime, and regulatory fines. For example, a DID system can lead to costly remediation efforts, including forensic investigations, legal expenses, and system repairs [105]. Additionally, organisations may face penalties for non-compliance with data protection laws, further straining financial resources. These impacts not only increase operational costs, but also jeopardise the financial stability of organisations, particularly if they are not prepared for such risks [105]. Mitigating these losses involves investing in preventive measures, such as fraud detection systems, regular audits, and comprehensive cybersecurity insurance [112].

6.2.2 Stock Variation

The indirect economic consequences of cyber incidents often manifest themselves as fluctuations in market value or stock prices for companies that provide or rely on DID systems [113]. Such variations may result from reputational damage, loss of investor confidence, or the financial consequence of a security breach. For example, news of a breach can lead to a sharp decrease in stock prices, signaling a decrease in trust between shareholders and the public [98]. Recovery from such incidents often requires significant efforts in reputation management and strategic communication. Organisations can mitigate stock-related risks by ensuring transparency, maintaining strong security measures, and demonstrating their commitment to safeguarding user data [70].

6.3 Societal Impact

Societal impacts outline a key dimension of risk within the cyber threat taxonomy for DID systems, highlighting the social repercussions of such threats. This component of the taxonomy highlights the social risks

associated with DID systems, emphasising the need for ethical practices, transparency, and robust security measures to protect public trust and social stability [14; 69; 114; 104]. The subcategories include:

6.3.1 Discrimination

DID systems carry the risk of perpetuating or exacerbating biases and inequalities, often through algorithmic decision making or systemic mismanagement [14; 106]. For example, algorithms used in identity verification processes may inadvertently favour certain demographics while disadvantaging others [13]. This risk highlights the importance of auditing systems for bias, improving algorithmic transparency, and ensuring equitable treatment for all individuals. Addressing discrimination is essential to foster inclusivity and prevent marginalisation within DID ecosystems.

6.3.2 Public Perception and Trust

The success of DID systems is heavily dependent on public trust, which can be severely compromised by privacy violations, data breaches, or perceived data misuse [114; 106]. Lack of transparency in how identity systems operate and protect user data can lead to skepticism and resistance to adoption [20]. Proactively building trust through clear communication, strong data protection policies, and demonstrable security practices is critical to ensuring the societal acceptance and sustained use of these systems [101].

6.3.3 Reputation Damage

Security incidents affecting DID systems can result in significant reputational damage to organisations, governments, or managing entities [69; 60]. A compromised reputation undermines public confidence, diminishes stakeholder support, and can lead to a loss of credibility on a national or global scale. Implementing comprehensive incident response plans and engaging in transparent communication during crises can help organisations mitigate reputational risks and rebuild trust after an incident [70; 115].

6.3.4 Misinformation & Disinformation Campaigns

DID systems can become tools for spreading false information or manipulating public opinion [14; 12]. Adversaries can exploit these systems to launch misinformation campaigns, undermine social trust, and destabilise governance structures. Countering this risk requires robust monitoring of system use, collaboration with media platforms to debunk false narratives, and public education campaigns to foster critical thinking and media literacy [42; 88].

6.4 Technological Impact

As DPI systems become more established, integrated, and widely adopted in society, they face escalating technological risks from increasingly sophisticated cyber threats [69]. When these systems are compromised, the consequences go beyond technical challenges, affecting societal trust, organisational stability, and regulatory compliance [20]. Interruptions in service availability can disrupt essential operations, leading to economic losses and reduced confidence in the reliability of public systems, as discussed above [104]. Furthermore, breaches that compromise data integrity undermine public trust in digital services, discouraging future adoption [24]. Organisations may also face financial losses, reputational damage, and significant regulatory penalties if they do not meet data protection and security standards [110]. Addressing these technological risks is critical to ensuring the resilience, security, and continued acceptance of DPI systems. The following is a detailed description of the technological impacts on DID systems:

6.4.1 DPI Service Disruption

DPI service disruptions (Figure 25) can severely impact the availability and functionality of identity systems, causing widespread problems for users who rely on these systems to access services. The following are details in this category:

Figure 19: DPI Service Disruption

6.4.1.1 Network Outage

Interruptions to the network infrastructure can cripple identity verification processes, making it impossible for people to authenticate themselves. Such disruptions may arise from physical damage to network cables, attacks on routers, or issues with Internet service providers [52].

6.4.1.2 Critical Application Failure

Identity systems often rely on complex applications that manage authentication, data storage, and access controls. Failure in these applications, whether due to software bugs, malicious code injection, or system overload, can stop identity services, disrupting essential functions such as access to e-Governance, banking, or healthcare [5].

6.4.1.3 Cloud Service Outages/Downtime

Many identity systems use cloud infrastructure for scalability and resilience [111]. However, outages in cloud service providers, due to misconfigurations, DDoS attacks, or hardware failures, can render identity systems inaccessible, affecting service delivery and trust in the infrastructure [68].

6.4.1.4 Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) Attacks

Attackers may flood identity service servers with an overwhelming amount of traffic, making them unavailable to legitimate users. This can prevent users from accessing essential services, disrupt operations, and potentially erode public confidence in digital infrastructure [84].

6.4.1.5 Supply Chain and Third-Party Disruption

DPI identity systems often depend on third-party vendors for software, hardware, or service support. If these suppliers are compromised, it can create vulnerabilities within the identity system [30]. Examples include compromised software updates or disruptions in the supply chain affecting hardware availability [5].

6.4.1.6 Backup and Disaster Recovery Disruption

Identity systems rely on backup and disaster recovery mechanisms to ensure data integrity and system resilience [115]. Disruptions in these processes, whether through sabotage, hardware failures, or ransomware attacks, can result in loss of critical data and delay system recovery [58].

6.4.2 DPI Data and Privacy Violation

Data and privacy violations (Figure 26) in DID systems pose significant risks, from personal data theft to large-scale breaches that can undermine public trust and lead to severe legal consequences [45; 5]. The following are detailed in this category:

Figure 20: DPI Data and Privacy Violation

6.4.2.1 Unauthorised Data Access

Gaining unauthorised access to identity databases allows attackers to extract sensitive information, including personal identification details, biometric data, and access credentials. Such breaches can facilitate identity fraud and other forms of cybercrime [45; 88].

6.4.2.2 Data Leak

Accidental or deliberate data leaks expose sensitive information to the public or unauthorised parties. Data leaks may occur through misconfigured databases, insider threats, or poorly secured backup systems. The exposure of personal identity data can have far-reaching implications, including loss of trust and financial liabilities [81; 106].

6.4.2.3 User Profiling and Tracking

Threat actors can use compromised identity systems to track user activities and create detailed profiles that can be used for targeted attacks, surveillance, or manipulation. This raises significant privacy concerns, particularly for vulnerable populations or individuals in sensitive roles [31; 1].

6.4.2.4 Compliance Breach

DID systems must adhere to strict regulatory frameworks, such as GDPR or local data protection laws. A breach of compliance due to mishandling or unauthorised access can result in substantial fines, legal action, and reputational damage to the organisation that manages the infrastructure [71; 45].

6.4.2.5 Biometric Data Compromise

As biometric data (e.g. fingerprints, facial recognition, iris scans) become increasingly used in identity systems, its compromise poses severe risks. Unlike passwords, biometric data cannot be easily changed, making the impact of such a breach long-lasting and difficult to mitigate [89; 91].

6.4.2.6 Fraud and Data Theft

Compromised identity systems can lead to fraud, including financial fraud, impersonation, and unauthorised transactions. Attackers may use stolen data to commit crimes or sell it on the black market, further endangering affected individuals and organisations [50; 5].

6.5 Legal Impact

This component of the taxonomy underscores the importance of adhering to legal standards and implementing governance mechanisms to mitigate potential legal risks related to cyber threats targeting DID systems. Figure 1 identifies a critical dimension of risk within the cyber threat taxonomy for DID systems, focusing on legal and regulatory consequences [110]. The subcategories include:

6.5.1 Legal/Compliance Violation

These risks arise when DID systems do not comply with legal frameworks, privacy laws, or regulatory requirements specific to the jurisdictions they operate in [114]. Non-compliance can result in lawsuits filed by affected individuals or organisations, financial penalties imposed by regulators, or enforcement actions such as operational restrictions. These violations not only cause financial losses but also damage the reputation of the organisation and undermine trust in the system [114].

6.5.2 Intellectual Property & Confidentiality Violation

Breaches involving unauthorised access to proprietary data, trade secrets, or confidential information jeopardise an organisation's intellectual property [24]. Such violations can occur due to insider threats, cyberattacks, or improper access controls. The misuse of sensitive information can lead to litigation, loss of competitive advantage, and reduced market trust. Additionally, the compromised data could be exploited for fraud, further exacerbating the impact on the organisation [114].

6.5.3 Regulatory & Legal Fees

DID organisations face significant financial burdens in the aftermath of legal challenges or compliance failures [14]. Costs may include legal defences against lawsuits, settlements with affected parties, fines for non-compliance, and penalties for mishandling sensitive DID data [110]. These expenses, coupled with

potential operational disruptions and reputational harm, can substantially strain resources and impede the organisation's ability to sustain its operations effectively [114].

6.6 Likelihood

The likelihood of risk in the context of DPI identity systems refers to the probability or chance that a specific threat or attack will occur. Understanding and evaluating the likelihood of different risks is crucial to prioritising security measures and effectively allocating resources [31]. The likelihood levels are classified as Critical, High, Medium, and Low, each reflecting the probability of occurrence based on current threat landscapes, the vulnerabilities of the system, and the attractiveness of the system to adversaries.

6.6.1 Critical

This level indicates that there is an almost certain chance that the threat will occur. Factors that contribute to a critical likelihood include high-value targets, known vulnerabilities, and the presence of persistent threats.

- *Highly Attractive Targets*: DPI identity systems store valuable data, such as personal and biometric information, making them prime targets for nation-state actors, cybercriminals, and hacktivists [110]. The critical nature of these data increases the likelihood of targeted attacks.
- *Persistent Threat Actors*: Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) from well-resourced adversaries, such as nation-states, are continuously seeking opportunities to infiltrate critical infrastructure [20]. Their persistence and use of sophisticated methods raise the likelihood of attacks.
- *Widespread Vulnerabilities*: If the system uses widely deployed technologies that are known to have vulnerabilities, the risk of an attack becomes critical. For example, an unpatched software vulnerability in a commonly used identity management system can attract numerous attack attempts [5].

6.6.2 High

This level represents a strong probability that a threat will occur, although not as certain as the critical level. High likelihood is associated with commonly exploited vulnerabilities and the increasing sophistication of adversaries.

- *Frequent Attack Attempts*: Identity systems are regularly subjected to attacks such as phishing, credential stuffing, or DDoS [68]. The high volume of these attacks, combined with the evolving tactics of the attackers, suggests a high probability of occurrence.
- *Commonly Known Vulnerabilities*: Security gaps that are widely recognised and easy to exploit increase the probability of attacks. Examples include weak password policies, misconfigured access controls, or the use of outdated encryption methods [83].
- *Integration with Other Critical Systems*: If the identity system is integrated with other critical national infrastructure, the potential for collateral attacks or breaches through interconnected systems increases the likelihood of a threat [24]. Attackers may target the weakest link in a chain of interconnected systems.

6.6.3 Moderate

A moderate likelihood indicates that a threat is possible but less frequent or likely to occur compared to high or critical risks. This level applies to threats that require specific conditions or a combination of factors to occur.

- *Conditional Risks*: Some threats require particular conditions, such as insider access or sophisticated social engineering, to be successful [84]. Although these risks are concerning, the likelihood that all conditions are met is moderate.
- *Less Exploitable Vulnerabilities*: When vulnerabilities are known, but require advanced knowledge or significant resources to exploit them, the probability of an attack may be moderate [91]. For example, vulnerabilities that are difficult to weaponise or require physical access fall into this category.
- *Periodic Threats*: Attacks that occur periodically, such as those aligned with significant events (e.g., elections or government policy changes), have a moderate likelihood. Although the frequency is lower, the impact can still be significant if taken advantage of [5].

6.6.4 Low

A low likelihood suggests that the probability that a threat occurs is minimal. This level often applies to well-secured systems with strong defences or to risks that are highly improbable.

- *Well-Defended Systems*: Identity systems that have implemented multiple layers of security, such as encryption, MFA, and continuous monitoring, are less likely to be successfully attacked [30]. The presence of strong defences deters many potential attackers.
- *Limited Incentive for Attack*: If the identity system does not store particularly valuable or exploitable data or if the cost of executing an attack outweighs the benefits, the likelihood is reduced [115]. For example, systems used for non-critical identity verification may not be an attractive target.
- *Uncommon Attack Vectors*: Risks involving highly specialised or uncommon attack vectors have a lower likelihood [20]. For example, attacks that require niche expertise or rare physical access may be considered to be of low probability.

7 Response Strategies

Response strategies for DPI based ID systems are designed to safeguard these critical systems against a wide array of cyber threats. These strategies range from immediate measures to long-term planning and governance, focussing on preventing, detecting, mitigating, and recovering from security incidents. A rigorous approach to response ensures the protection of sensitive identity information and the continuous availability of public services. Here is a detailed breakdown of the response strategies:

7.1 Preventative and Mitigation Strategies

Effective response strategies are essential to minimise the damage caused by cyber attacks and ensure rapid recovery.

- *Immediate strategies*: These are rapid actions taken to contain threats and mitigate damage. Examples include incident response teams mobilising to isolate affected systems, deploying patches to fix vulnerabilities, and using multi-factor authentication to secure access points [112; 70]. Incident response playbooks should be regularly updated to handle new and emerging threats [98; 115].
- *Mid-Term strategies*: Focused on strengthening the overall security posture of the organisation. This includes continuous monitoring of network activity [113], conducting regular security training sessions for employees [112], and performing routine audits to identify weaknesses. Organisations should also update their policies and procedures based on lessons learnt from past incidents [98].

- *Long-Term strategies:* These involve building a comprehensive and sustainable defence framework. Measures include system hardening [113], investing in R&D to develop advanced security solutions [112], and fostering international collaborations for the sharing of threat intelligence [70]. Long-term strategies also emphasise governance and compliance, ensuring that security practices align with industry standards and evolving regulatory requirements [115].

7.1.1 Immediate Strategies

Immediate strategies are designed to provide a rapid and effective response to security incidents, ensuring that threats are quickly identified, contained, and mitigated to minimise damage. These strategies focus on real-time actions and countermeasures that address both the immediate impact of an incident and the prevention of further escalation. As shown in Figure 21, the figure for immediate strategies includes the deployment of detective controls to identify anomalies and suspicious activities, the execution of containment measures to isolate affected systems and prevent the spread of attacks, and the implementation of corrective controls to restore normalcy and address vulnerabilities [115; 84; 30; 105]. In addition, preventive controls serve to reduce the likelihood of recurring incidents by strengthening the defences of the system [104; 84]. Together, these measures establish a comprehensive and agile approach to incident response, enabling DID organisations to protect their systems against evolving threats effectively [71; 69].

Figure 21: Immediate Strategies

7.1.1.1 Detective Controls

These controls are designed to quickly identify and respond to security incidents. They involve continuous monitoring and the use of advanced threat detection systems, such as intrusion detection systems (IDS) and Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) tools [84; 115]. These systems analyse network traffic and user behaviour in real time to detect potential threats [105; 30]. These controls play a key role in maintaining visibility and enabling timely responses to suspicious activities, ensuring that incidents are promptly identified and investigated.

7.1.1.2 Containment

Upon detection of a threat, immediate containment measures are taken to isolate affected systems and prevent the spread of the attack [24]. This may involve disconnecting compromised systems from the network, disabling user accounts that are under attack, or rerouting network traffic to mitigate a DDoS attack [84]. Effective containment is critical to limiting the impact of an attack and reducing the likelihood of further damage to the system.

7.1.1.3 Corrective Controls

These controls focus on restoring normal operations and minimising damage after a security incident [101; 71]. They include measures like rolling back to previous or updated configurations, patching vulnerabilities, and removing malicious code [31; 105]. These controls include activities such as post-incident recovery, which ensures the restoration of systems and business processes, and root cause analysis, which identifies the underlying reasons for the incident to inform long-term solutions [30]. Corrective controls also incorporate incident response plans that define structured steps to handle incidents effectively and forensic analysis to investigate breaches and derive lessons learnt [101; 84]. Metrics such as Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF), Mean Time to Detect (MTTD), Mean Time to Acknowledge (MTTA), Mean Time to Contain (MTTC), and Mean Time to Resolve (MTTR) are essential for measuring the effectiveness of these controls [101]. In addition, these measures facilitate stakeholder reporting and ensure that learning is applied to improve system security against future incidents.

7.1.1.4 Preventative Controls

Actions taken to prevent future incidents, such as implementing firewalls, implementing strong authentication methods, and performing regular software updates [31; 104]. Preventive controls also include enforcing least-privilege access and using endpoint protection solutions [101; 84]. These measures are essential for creating a secure system environment and reducing the likelihood of successful attacks.

7.1.2 Mid-Term Strategies

Mid-term strategies, as depicted in Figure 22, are designed to address the evolving security needs of DID systems by implementing robust, scalable, and sustainable measures. These strategies focus on improving organisational resilience, nurturing a culture of security, and staying ahead of emerging threats [84]. Unlike immediate responses, mid-term approaches involve the integration of advanced technologies, structured processes, and collaborative practices that ensure ongoing adaptability and effectiveness [24]. The following subsections outline key components of mid-term strategies, including monitoring and detection, training and awareness programmes, audits and risk assessments, threat intelligence integration, policy updates, and access review practices. Together, these initiatives aim to fortify DID systems against a wide array of challenges while ensuring compliance with regulatory standards and maintaining public trust [24]. The mid-term strategies include the following.

Figure 22: Mid-Term Strategies

7.1.2.1 *Monitoring and Detection*

Effective monitoring and detection are critical to identifying and mitigating new threats to DID systems [69]. Continuous surveillance systems leverage technologies such as anomaly detection, log analysis, and automated alerts to identify suspicious activities in real time [30]. These systems enable a rapid response to potential security breaches by detecting unusual patterns or behaviours. Integrating advanced monitoring tools with incident response mechanisms ensures a proactive approach to threat detection, minimising the impact of emerging risks on system integrity [84].

7.1.2.2 *Training and Awareness Programmes*

Human error remains a significant vulnerability in security systems, making training and awareness programmes essential [84]. Regular security training educates employees and end users about recognising phishing attempts, securely handling sensitive data, and adhering to security best practices. Tailored training sessions that address specific user roles and potential risks enhance understanding and foster a culture of security [24]. By empowering people with knowledge, these programmes significantly reduce the likelihood of preventable incidents [69].

7.1.2.3 *Audit and Risk Assessment*

Periodic audits and risk assessments are vital to maintaining a secure and compliant DID system [24]. Audits provide an objective evaluation of current security measures, while risk assessments identify potential vulnerabilities and threats. These activities help organisations understand their security posture and prioritise areas for improvement. By addressing the gaps identified during audits and assessments, systems can remain resilient against evolving risks and comply with regulatory standards [30].

7.1.2.4 *Threat Intelligence Integration*

Integrating threat intelligence into security strategies equips organisations with up-to-date information on emerging attack methods, indicators of compromise (IoCs), and vulnerabilities [68]. By analysing these data, security teams can anticipate and mitigate potential threats more effectively [84]. Threat intelligence also improves decision making by providing actionable insights that inform proactive defence measures. Leveraging intelligence from trusted sources strengthens the overall resilience of the DID system against advanced and targeted attacks [24].

7.1.2.5 *Policy Updates and Documentation*

Security policies, protocols, and procedures must be regularly reviewed and updated to reflect evolving threats and compliance requirements [115]. Clear and comprehensive documentation ensures that all stakeholders understand their role in maintaining security and responding to incidents. Keeping policies aligned with the latest standards, such as GDPR or ISO 27001, demonstrates a commitment to security and accountability [69]. Up-to-date documentation also facilitates the consistent implementation of best practices throughout the organisation [84].

7.1.2.6 *Access Review and Privilege Management*

Regular access reviews and privilege management practices minimise the risk of unauthorised access and insider threats [30]. By ensuring that users only have access to information necessary for their roles, organisations reduce the attack surface and limit potential damage in the event of a security breach. Automated tools for access management and periodic user privilege audits enhance transparency and accountability [69]. Privilege management is a cornerstone of secure system design, safeguarding sensitive resources and maintaining trust [101].

7.1.3 Long-Term Strategies

Long-term strategies, as depicted in Figure 23 aim to establish long-term security and resilience for DID systems by addressing the foundational infrastructure, evolving threats, and future technological advancements [104]. These strategies focus on creating systems that can adapt to changing security landscapes and withstand potential disruptions over time. By focussing on principles such as system hardening, trustworthy infrastructure, continuous vulnerability management, and compliance, these measures ensure the integrity and reliability of DID systems [31]. In addition, the adoption of architectural innovations such as the Zero-Trust model [30], partnerships with strategic vendors, and investments in research and development allow organisations to proactively address emerging DPI risks. Incorporating crisis management and business continuity planning further ensures that critical services remain operational during unforeseen challenges [24]. Together, these long-term strategies create a framework designed to support the sustained growth and security of DID ecosystems.

Figure 23: Long-Term Strategies

7.1.3.1 System Hardening

System hardening focusses on fortifying the DID system by minimising potential vulnerabilities [31]. This involves removing unnecessary services, applying secure configurations, and integrating advanced protection mechanisms such as intrusion detection systems and endpoint security tools [24]. Regularly auditing and updating the system settings to align with evolving security standards ensures resilience against various attack vectors. By proactive addressing potential weaknesses, the hardening of the system establishes a robust foundation that mitigates risks and protects the integrity of the identity infrastructure [30].

7.1.3.2 Trustworthy and Resilient Infrastructure

A trustworthy and resilient infrastructure is essential to maintain service availability and reliability even in the face of attacks or failures [24]. This requires the implementation of redundant systems to prevent single points of failure, secure data backups to ensure data recovery, and comprehensive disaster recovery plans to address large-scale incidents. Incorporating high availability architectures and real-time monitoring strengthens the system's ability to withstand disruptions while maintaining user trust and continuity of service [69].

7.1.3.3 Continuous Vulnerability Management

Continuous vulnerability management involves an ongoing cycle of identifying, assessing and mitigating security vulnerabilities [84]. Automated tools, such as vulnerability scanners, can regularly inspect the system for weaknesses, while penetration testing provides a deeper understanding of potential attack paths. The timely application of security patches and updates is critical to addressing identified vulnerabilities [24]. By embedding this process into routine operations, DID systems can remain protected against newly discovered threats and minimise potential exploitation risks [107].

7.1.3.4 Compliance

Compliance with relevant laws and regulations, such as GDPR, is crucial to maintaining user trust and avoiding legal consequences [14]. This involves conducting regular audits, maintaining detailed records, and implementing processes to ensure data protection and privacy [111]. Working closely with regulatory bodies and staying up-to-date on emerging legal requirements ensures that security practices remain aligned with the latest standards. Compliance not only protects users, but also reinforces the credibility and accountability of the DID system [115].

7.1.3.5 Architectural Development (Zero-Trust)

The Zero-Trust security model strengthens DID systems by enforcing a principle of "never trust, always verify" [24]. Every access request is authenticated, authorised, and encrypted regardless of its origin. This model emphasises the least privilege access, where users and systems have only the permissions necessary for their roles. Zero-Trust architectures also include micro-segmentation to isolate sensitive resources and prevent lateral movement within the network, ensuring a robust and proactive defence against potential breaches [30].

7.1.3.6 Vendor and Strategic Alliances

Partnering with reputable vendors and forming strategic alliances enhance the security capabilities of DID systems [115]. This includes thorough due diligence to ensure that third-party providers adhere to high-security standards and implement secure development practices. Collaborative partnerships also allow organisations to leverage advanced technologies, shared threat intelligence, and expert guidance to strengthen their overall security posture and operational efficiency [5].

7.1.3.7 R&D for Novel Techniques and Frameworks

Investing in research and development is essential to stay ahead of evolving threats [31]. This includes exploring advanced encryption methods, developing innovative security frameworks, and employing AI and machine learning for predictive threat detection [84]. Collaborating with academia, industry experts and think tanks promotes innovation and provides cutting-edge tools and strategies that enhance the security and resilience of DID systems [63].

7.1.3.8 Crisis Management and Business Continuity

Establishing a crisis management and business continuity framework ensures that critical identity services remain operational during incidents [52]. This involves creating detailed response plans for potential crises, such as cyberattacks or natural disasters, and conducting regular drills to test preparedness. Business continuity planning includes identifying critical services, ensuring rapid restoration capabilities, and maintaining secure backups [101]. These measures protect the confidence of the stakeholders in the ID system during challenging situations [30].

7.2 Governance and Management

Governance and management encompass the policies, frameworks, and operational practices necessary to oversee and maintain the security and functionality of DID systems. This involves ensuring public trust through transparent communication, efficient management of resources, and collaborative decision-making with stakeholders. Effective governance establishes accountability, promotes compliance with regulatory standards, and addresses evolving security challenges. Strong operational management focusses on streamlining processes, improving system efficiency, and mitigating risks to ensure the resilience of identity systems.

7.2.1 Public Trust and Communication Management

Public trust and communication management are essential components to maintaining the credibility and adoption of DID systems. These efforts focus on fostering user confidence through transparency, security, and proactive engagement while addressing challenges such as misinformation and crisis scenarios. As shown in Figure 24, strategies in this area aim to build a strong foundation of trust, effectively manage disinformation, respond to crises with clear communication, and protect the reputation of the system. Together, these measures ensure that DID systems are perceived as reliable, secure, and user-focused, reinforcing public confidence and encouraging widespread adoption.

Figure 24: Public Trust and Communication Management

7.2.1.1 Develop Public Trust

Building public trust requires a foundation of transparency, security, and consistent communication. DID systems should emphasise the protection of personal data by demonstrating compliance with privacy regulations and employing robust security measures such as encryption and authentication protocols. Public education initiatives, such as workshops and awareness campaigns, play a critical role in highlighting the benefits and safeguards of the system, ensuring that users are informed and engaged. Establishing feedback mechanisms allows users to report concerns and fosters a sense of accountability. These practices collectively improve user confidence, encouraging adoption and reinforcing the system's credibility [116].

7.2.1.2 Misinformation and Disinformation Management

Misinformation and disinformation can erode public confidence in DID systems, making it essential to effectively counter such threats. Implementing tools for monitoring on-line platforms helps identify false narratives before they gain traction. Dedicated teams can quickly address disinformation by fact-checking and disseminating accurate information to the public. Educational campaigns enable users to recognise and question misleading content, fostering a more informed user base. Collaborating with media organisations and social media platforms further strengthens efforts to combat misinformation, ensuring the integrity of the identity system is maintained [117].

7.2.1.3 Crisis Communication

During crises, such as data breaches or system failures, clear and transparent communication is vital to maintaining public trust. A well-prepared crisis management plan outlines roles, responsibilities, and communication protocols, allowing swift and organised responses. Providing timely updates to affected parties reassures users and mitigates speculation. Collaborating with media outlets ensures accurate and consistent messaging, reducing the spread of misinformation during critical times. Post-crisis evaluations are essential to refine communication strategies and improve future preparedness. Effective crisis communication demonstrates the resilience and commitment of the system to transparency, reassuring users and stakeholders [118].

7.2.1.4 Reputation Management Strategies

Reputation management is important, particularly after incidents that can undermine user trust. Engaging stakeholders through regular updates and transparent communication reinforces confidence in the system. Prompt public statements addressing incidents should detail the nature of the problem, the measures taken to resolve it, and the steps implemented to prevent recurrence. Highlighting ongoing improvements, such as system audits or new security certifications, demonstrates a commitment to maintaining high standards. Long-term reputation recovery efforts, including trust building campaigns, emphasise transparency and reliability, ensuring sustained public confidence in the identity system [116].

7.2.2 Operational Efficiency and Compliance Management

Operational efficiency and compliance management are essential to ensure the sustainability and security of DID systems. These aspects focus on optimising resource utilisation, maintaining robust supply chain security, and adhering to regulatory standards. As illustrated in Figure 25, these components collectively aim to strengthen the resilience and reliability of DID systems while ensuring alignment with organisational and legal requirements [119; 120]. In the following, the key factors of resource allocation and supply chain management are expanded to highlight their critical roles.

Figure 25: Operational Efficiency and Compliance Management

7.2.2.1 Resource Allocation

Efficient resource allocation supports the ability to manage and mitigate security risks effectively. This involves strategic planning and distribution of financial, human, and technical resources to ensure the readiness of the system for cybersecurity. Budgeting for cybersecurity investments, such as advanced monitoring tools and secure infrastructure upgrades, is essential to address evolving threats. In addition, ensuring that skilled personnel and technical support are readily available for incident response and system maintenance enhances operational resilience. Resource allocation also includes contingency planning, ensuring that funds and capabilities are reserved for unforeseen security challenges. By aligning resources with prioritised risks, organisations can achieve an optimal balance between cost efficiency and robust security measures [119].

7.2.2.2 Supply Chain Management

Supply chain management is critical in safeguarding the integrity of DID systems by addressing potential vulnerabilities introduced by third-party vendors and supply chain partners. This process involves conducting comprehensive supplier risk assessments to assess their security practices and identify potential threats. Continuous monitoring of supply chain activities ensures that emerging risks, such as compromised components or services, are promptly addressed. Contract management also plays a key role, with security requirements explicitly outlined and enforced to hold vendors accountable. Building strong partnerships with suppliers who meet stringent security standards minimises supply chain risks and fortifies the overall security framework of the DID system [120].

7.2.3 Collaborative and Diplomatic Factors

Collaborative and diplomatic factors emphasise the importance of partnerships, communication, and international cooperation in enhancing the security and operational resilience of DID systems. These factors leverage shared intelligence, strategic alliances, and stakeholder relationships to address challenges that extend beyond organisational or national boundaries. As illustrated in Figure 26, such collaborative efforts foster unified and coordinated approaches to cybersecurity, ensuring that various entities work together to achieve common security objectives. In the following, the aspects of international collaboration and relationship management are elaborated to highlight their importance [118; 120].

Figure 26: Collaborative and Diplomatic Factors

7.2.3.1 *International Collaboration*

International collaboration is vital to address cyber threats that transcend national boundaries. By engaging with global partners and participating in international cybersecurity initiatives, organisations can benefit from shared threat intelligence and collective expertise. Collaborative efforts enable the development of standardised approaches to risk mitigation, ensuring consistent responses across borders. In addition, international partnerships facilitate the pooling of resources and the establishment of best practices for addressing emerging threats. This global cooperation improves preparedness and helps organisations stay ahead of sophisticated cyber adversaries [118].

7.2.3.2 *Relationship Management*

Effective relationship management strengthens coordination and response efforts by bringing trust and communication between key stakeholders. Establishing strong ties with government agencies, private sector partners, and international organisations ensures collaboration with intelligence sharing during security incidents. Regular participation in joint exercises, workshops, and forums helps maintain these relationships and align priorities. Clear communication channels between stakeholders enable timely decision making and efficient allocation of resources during crises. By building and maintaining these relationships, ID organisations can create a networked defence strategy that improves the security of DID systems [120].

7.2.4 Security and Governance Factors

Security and governance factors encompass the foundational elements that ensure the operational efficiency, resilience, and compliance of DID systems. These factors are essential in maintaining trust, safeguarding national security, and complying with legal and regulatory requirements. As illustrated in Figure 27, these components provide a structured approach to address the security challenges of DID ecosystems while aligning with governance principles. The following subsections elaborate on key aspects, such as national security and compliance management, which play a pivotal role in the protection of the integrity and reliability of identity systems [118; 116].

7.2.4.1 *National Security*

National security considerations in DID systems focus on safeguarding critical infrastructure and ensuring the

Figure 27: Security and Governance Factors

resilience of identity services against state-sponsored attacks, cyber terrorism, and espionage [118]. DID systems are often integral to essential public services, making them high-value targets for adversaries.

- *State-Sponsored Threats:* Protection involves deploying advanced security measures, such as encryption and intrusion detection, to counter sophisticated attacks from hostile states [101].
- *Resilience:* Ensuring uninterrupted service delivery through robust disaster recovery plans and redundant systems helps mitigate the impact of potential threats [101].
- *Collaboration:* Partnerships between government agencies, private sectors and international organisations are crucial to sharing intelligence and coordinating responses to cyber threats [5].

Aligning DID security with national priorities ensures not only the robustness of the system, but also the protection of citizens' data and trust in government services [118].

7.2.4.2 Compliance and Regulation

Compliance and regulation are essential for maintaining the legitimacy and accountability of DID systems. By adhering to laws such as GDPR and other regional frameworks, organisations demonstrate their commitment to secure and ethical data management [116].

- *Policy Development:* Establishing clear policies that address data protection, user consent, and breach notification requirements ensures alignment with legal mandates [118].
- *Regular Audits:* Conducting periodic reviews of security practices and compliance policies helps identify and address gaps proactively [24].
- *Regulatory Engagement:* Actively collaborating with regulatory bodies ensures that the system adapts to evolving legal landscapes and incorporates the latest best practices [24].
- *Transparency:* Clear documentation and communication with stakeholders about compliance measures build trust and facilitate accountability [84].

By embedding compliance into the governance structure, DID systems can minimise legal risks, improve operational efficiency, and foster public confidence [116].

7.3 Response Level and Cost

The response level categorises the urgency and extent of strategies required to address varying levels of risk in DPI-based identity systems [24]. Each level reflects the severity of potential threats and describes the corresponding measures to mitigate associated risks. In addition, the financial and operational impacts of these strategies are considered to ensure efficient resource allocation [105]. The cost of implementing response strategies includes both direct and indirect expenses. Direct costs include investments in security infrastructure, the hiring of cybersecurity professionals, and the purchase of advanced threat detection systems.

Indirect costs, such as potential downtime, loss of productivity, reputational damage, and compliance-related expenses, must also be evaluated. Effective risk management requires a balanced approach, ensuring that financial investments align with the potential impact of unmitigated threats while maintaining operational and economic stability [121].

7.3.1 Critical

Critical risks represent the most severe threats, including large-scale data breaches, system-wide outages, or attacks that compromise national security [30]. Addressing these risks requires immediate and comprehensive responses, such as implementing emergency response plans, real-time threat containment, and deploying advanced threat intelligence solutions [101]. These efforts often require collaboration with government agencies and mobilising all available resources. Although the financial and operational costs, including emergency response teams, advanced technologies, and potential service disruptions, are substantial, failing to address these threats could result in even more devastating financial losses, regulatory fines, and erosion of public trust [24].

7.3.2 High

High-level threats are serious and can cause significant harm, such as targeted cyber-attacks or breaches that affect a large portion of the user base of the identity system [68]. Addressing these risks involves rapid response measures, including enhanced monitoring, patching of vulnerabilities, and deploying additional security controls [84]. Coordination with external security experts or vendors may also be required. Although the cost of mitigation is considerable, covering investments in advanced threat detection, incident response planning, and continuous security assessments, it is essential to prevent major data breaches or disruptions and ensure system resilience [5].

7.3.3 Medium

Medium-level threats pose risks to the integrity, confidentiality, or availability of the system, but are less likely to cause immediate damage [24]. These threats are managed through regular security updates, ongoing monitoring, and staff training programmes to increase awareness of potential risks. Preventive and corrective measures, such as software updates and vulnerability scans, are generally sufficient without requiring emergency intervention [84]. The associated costs are moderate and often include routine security measures and cost-effective solutions that balance adequate protection with minimal financial strain.

7.3.4 Low

Low-level threats have a minimal likelihood of causing significant damage and often involve minor vulnerabilities or risks [101]. These are typically addressed as part of standard system maintenance through basic security hygiene practices, periodic reviews, and patching known vulnerabilities [69]. Monitoring low-level risks over time ensures that they do not escalate. The costs associated with addressing these risks are relatively low and generally fall within the standard operating budget, covering minor software upgrades, routine maintenance, and basic cybersecurity training [101].

7.4 Countermeasure Maturity Level

The countermeasure maturity level provides a structured framework to assess the development and comprehensiveness of security measures implemented to protect DPI identity systems [104; 122]. It enables organisations to evaluate their current security posture, identify areas that need improvement, and guide

strategic decisions to strengthen their defences. This framework categorises the maturity of security measures into progressive levels, highlighting the evolution from obsolete or underdeveloped controls to mature, widely implemented defences [24].

7.4.1 Not Applicable

Some security measures may not align with the specific operational requirements, risk profile, or strategic objectives of a particular infrastructure [101]. In such cases, these controls are deemed unnecessary and omitted to focus resources on more impactful measures. Organisations at this level ensure that their efforts are concentrated on deploying countermeasures that address relevant risks effectively, avoiding resource misallocation while maintaining security efficiency [84].

7.4.2 Depreciated/Obsolete

Security measures categorised as deprecated or obsolete no longer meet the necessary standards to protect against modern threats [101]. These controls may introduce vulnerabilities due to outdated technologies or techniques. Organisations operating at this level prioritise retiring and replacing these measures with contemporary solutions [30]. This transition often includes evaluating current threats and aligning upgrades with industry standards to ensure adequate protection [104].

7.4.3 Limited Availability

This level indicates a lack of access to certain critical security controls or incomplete implementation of available measures [24]. Infrastructures at this stage are subject to increased exposure to threats. Organisations address this by identifying and bridging security gaps, prioritising the development and deployment of foundational measures such as firewalls, authentication mechanisms, and encryption protocols to establish a strong baseline of protection [69].

7.4.4 Under Development

Security measures at this stage are in the process of being developed or deployed, but have not yet reached full implementation [115]. Although progress is evident, gaps remain, leaving systems vulnerable in certain areas. Implementers at this level focus on accelerating the implementation of high priority measures while conducting ongoing assessments to refine and adapt their strategies for complete coverage [31].

7.4.5 Available

At this level, security measures are readily accessible for deployment, allowing organisations to respond quickly to evolving threats. This availability facilitates dynamic adjustments to security postures, enabling rapid scaling of protections as needed. Organisations leverage this flexibility to adopt advanced technologies and frameworks that enhance the adaptability of their defences [101; 69].

7.4.6 Further Research

Security measures at this stage are functional, but may not fully address emerging or advanced threats. Organisations operating at this level invest in research and development to explore innovative technologies and refine existing controls. This process often involves testing emerging solutions, gathering threat intelligence, and incorporating advancements into their security strategies to stay ahead of evolving risks [30; 63].

7.4.7 Implemented

Successfully implemented security measures are operational and capable of mitigating known threats. However, they may require periodic updates to remain effective as the threat landscape evolves. Ensuring continued success involves maintaining regular monitoring and conducting periodic reviews to adapt measures to emerging challenges [24; 84].

7.4.8 Widely Implemented

Widely implemented measures represent a mature and integrated security posture in which defences are standardised. At this level, systems focus on optimising the efficiency and scalability of their controls while adapting them to address evolving operational and risk management needs. Such measures reflect an advanced state of readiness, ensuring comprehensive protection for DPI identity systems [104; 69].

8 Limitations

This section aims to propose the limitations of the taxonomy by describing the shortcomings such as comprehensiveness and applicability; thereby offering avenues for further refinement and development. Although the taxonomy serves as a foundational framework, the following limitations reflect challenges encountered during its formulation and the complex nature of the DID landscape. Key limitations are outlined below to provide context, ensuring that readers can interpret the taxonomy with a balanced understanding of its scope and constraints.

- *Restricted Search Scope:* The taxonomy development relied on a limited number of databases and sources for literature review and data collection. Although efforts were made to select the most relevant and comprehensive sources in the domain of digital identities, this restriction may have led to the omission of valuable studies indexed in alternative or less commonly used repositories.
- *Inclusion of Non-Peer-Reviewed Documents:* A proportion of the reviewed documents were not peer reviewed, including industry reports, case studies, and news articles. Although this approach broadens the perspective and incorporates practical insights, it may reduce the overall scientific rigour of the taxonomy. The inclusion of such sources aimed to reflect a more comprehensive view of the DID ecosystem, particularly in emerging threat scenarios.
- *Keyword Identification Challenges:* The selection of keywords for the literature search was based on a brief and largely unstructured review of relevant terminology. Although informed by expert experience, this approach may have overlooked critical terms or phrases, leading to the inadvertent exclusion of non-published studies on threats to DID systems.
- *Subjectivity in Document Screening:* The process of screening documents to determine their relevance involved subjective judgments about the potential contribution of each paper. Despite efforts to maintain objectivity, this subjectivity may have resulted in the exclusion of some papers that could have provided some insights into the taxonomy.
- *Rapid Review Methodology:* The development of the taxonomy was based on a rapid review of the selected documents. Although sufficient for generating a comprehensive classification, an iterative refinement process is essential to enhance and maintain the accuracy and conceptual clarity of the taxonomy.
- *Limited Representation of Emerging Threats:* The dynamic and evolving nature of DID systems means that new threats and attack vectors may not yet be documented in the literature or real world reports. As a result, the taxonomy may not fully represent nascent risks or region-specific vulnerabilities, particularly those arising from cutting-edge technologies or unique sociopolitical contexts.
- *Integration with Existing Frameworks:* Aligning the taxonomy with established security frameworks such as ISO 27001, NIST, or OWASP may introduce challenges due to differences in terminology, classifications, and threat modelling approaches.

9 Conclusion

The taxonomy presented for DID systems offers a structured approach to identifying and mitigating threats, assessing risks, and implementing appropriate response strategies. By categorising threats, risks, and response mechanisms, this taxonomy equips stakeholders, particularly decision-makers, with the tools needed to address the growing challenges posed by the evolving DID threat landscape.

Key developments emphasise the importance of understanding the motivations behind adversarial actions, which include financial gain, political influence, and intelligence gathering. Identifying attack points across software, hardware, and social engineering helps to develop targeted mitigation measures, enhancing resilience against sophisticated threats. Furthermore, the taxonomy stresses the need for continuous monitoring and proactive defence mechanisms to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of DID systems.

This structured and holistic approach supports executive decision making, helping organisations align their strategic planning with the identified risks and response needs. By fostering cross-sector collaboration and adopting best practices, stakeholders can improve the overall DID infrastructure, thus increasing the trustworthiness of DPs in an increasingly interconnected world.

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Appendix A: Threats in Focus

Table A1: Table of threats to digital ID system

S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Adversary	Attack Point	Attack Vector	Readiness Level	Difficulty	People, Process or Technology	Impact Areas	Attack Motivation	Affected Components
1	[72]	Credential Theft	Internal, External	User accounts, Identity Management System (IMS)	Manipulate data structures, Subvert access control, Collect and analyse information	Real-life incident (e.g., SolarWinds, LinkedIn, Parler breaches)	Password hacking tools such as bruteforce and wordlists such as rockyou.txt make this attack feasible	Technology (compromised infrastructure), People (stolen identities), Process (service disruptions)	Fraud and identity theft, Service disruption, Financial, Reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication mechanisms, Identity repositories (IMS), User devices
2	[78]	Insider Sabotage	Internal	Manufacturing Operating System	Abuse existing functionality	Real-life incident (Tesla 2018)	Requires insider access and system knowledge	Process (sabotaged operations)	Service disruption, potential reputation damage, financial loss	Financial Gain (as in the Tesla incident)	Authentication mechanism, data repositories
3	[74]	Credential Theft - Credential Stuffing	External	User Authentication	Engage in Deceptive Interaction (bot-driven brute force testing of credentials)	Real-life incident	Easy to prevent in current systems	Process (User Authentication)	Fraud and identity theft, reputation damage	Financial Gain	Authentication mechanism, data repositories
4	[74]	Credential Theft - Password Spraying	External	User Authentication	Engage in Deceptive Interaction (common passwords to gain access)	Real-life incident	Easy to prevent in current systems	Process (User Authentication)	Fraud and identity theft, financial impact	Financial Gain	Authentication mechanism, data repositories
5	[74]	Malware and Trojan Attacks	External	User Device	Inject unexpected items (malware/trojan injection)	Real-life incident	Not difficult but requires more resources than credential protection	Process (User Device)	Financial loss, identity theft	Financial Gain	User Device, Authentication mechanism
6	[74]	Phishing Attack	External	User Interaction	Engage in Deceptive Interaction (Phishing emails)	Real-life incident	Easy	People (User interaction)	Fraud and identity theft, reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	User Device, Authentication Mechanism
7	[74]	Insider Attacks	Internal	Data Repositories	Subvert access control	Real-life incident	Not difficult but cannot be executed many times	Process (data access and modification)	Legal/compliance violation, reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	Data repositories, authentication mechanism
8	[74]	Cryptojacking	External	User Device (browser hijacking)	Inject unexpected items (JavaScript code injection)	Real-life incident	Not easy	People (Stolen identities)	Fraud and identity theft, Service disruption, Financial loss	Financial Gain (cryptocurrency mining)	User Device, API and integration

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Threat Categories	Attack Point	Attack Vector	Readiness Level for Threat	Difficulty to Execute	People, Process or Technology	Impact Areas	Attack Motivation	Affected Components
9	[74]	Stealing Clicks	External	User Device	Engage in Deceptive Interaction (exploitation of user input for multi-factor authentication)	Real-life incident	Not easy	People (Stolen identities)	Fraud and identity theft	Financial Gain	User Device, Authentication mechanism
10	[74]	Network Availability Attack	External	Infrastructure (DNS spoofing, DDoS)	Manipulate system resources (exploiting network vulnerabilities)	Real-life incident	High	Process (network disruption)	Service disruption, financial loss, reputation damage	Disruption, Financial Gain	API and integration, data repositories
11	[74]	MITM Attack	External	Infrastructure (Intercepting encrypted communications)	Engage in Deceptive Interaction (session hijacking, eavesdropping)	Real-life incident	High	Process (Data interception, Session hijacking)	Fraud and identity theft, financial loss	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication mechanism, API and integration
12	[74]	51% Attack	Internal, External	Blockchain Infrastructure	Manipulate system resources (gain control of mining power or validators)	Real-life incident (Proof-of-Work blockchain attacks)	High (requires control over 51% of network)	Technology (blockchain network)	Fraud and identity theft, financial loss, reputation damage	Financial Gain, Disruption	Data repositories
13	[11]	Identity-Based and Social Engineering Attacks	External	Credential, API keys, session cookies, one-time passwords (OTPs), Kerberos tickets	Abuse existing functionality, Engage in deceptive interaction	Real-life incident	Not easy	Process	Identity theft, fraud, reputation damage	Financial gain, espionage	Authentication mechanism, API and integration
14	[11]	Cloud-Centric Attacks	External	Cloud configurations, Cloud storage	Manipulate system resources, abuse existing functionality	Real-life incident	High (requires cloud expertise)	Technology	Service disruption, data exfiltration, reputation damage	Financial gain, espionage	Data repositories, APIs, cloud resources
15	[11]	Supply Chain Attacks	External	Third-party software, vendor access	Subvert access control, abuse existing functionality	Real-life incident	High	Process and Technology	Service disruption, financial loss, legal/compliance violation	Financial gain, espionage, disruption	Vendor software, API and integration
16	[11]	Election Targeting	External	Voting systems, voter registration databases, government websites	Engage in deceptive interaction (disinformation), subvert access control (voting systems), collect and analyse information (voter data)	Real-life incident	Difficulty to execute	Process	Reputation damage, service disruption, fraud and identity theft	Political or ideological advantage, disruption	Data repositories, authentication mechanism (voter ID systems), government IT infrastructure

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Threat Categories	Attack Point	Attack Vector	Readiness Level for Threat	Difficulty to Execute	People, Process or Technology	Impact Areas	Attack Motivation	Affected Components
17	[102]	ARCHER Supercomputer Attack (Misuse of User Accounts)	External	User Authentication	Subvert access control, Manipulate system resources	Real-life incident	Medium (requires exploiting credentials, feasible for skilled attackers)	Technology	Service disruption, fraud and identity theft, reputation damage	Espionage, Disruption (including targeting of sensitive research like COVID-19 vaccine)	Authentication Mechanism, API and Integration Points, Data Repositories
18	[91; 92]	DeepFake Voice Spoofing	External	User Authentication (voice)	Manipulate Data Structures, Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Experimental	High (generating high-quality DeepFake)	Technology	Fraud and identity theft, Legal/compliance violation, Reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage, Disruption	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
19	[88]	Disclosure of Identity Data	External	Cached privacy-related information	Collect and analyse information	Real-life incident	Medium (possible with phishing and social engineering techniques)	People	Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage, Legal/compliance violation	Financial Gain, Espionage	Data Repositories, API and Integration Points
20	[123]	ID Database Compromised	External	Aadhaar System	Manipulate Data Structures, Subvert Access Control	Real-life incident	Not high	Process, People	Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage, Legal/compliance violation	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories
21	[124]	Privileged Account Compromise	Internal, External	Privileged accounts	Abuse existing functionality	Real-life incident (such as Edward Snowden case)	High (requires a combination of social engineering or internal exploitation)	Process, People	Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage, Legal/compliance violation	Financial gain, Espionage, Disruption	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories, API and Integration Points
22	[125]	Surveillance	External	Digital tracking and monitoring tools	Collect and analyse information, Subvert access control	Real-life incident	Medium	Technology	Legal/compliance violation, Reputation damage	Espionage, Disruption	User Devices, Authentication Mechanism
23	[89]	Facial Print Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Camera input (facial scan)	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Experiment	Low	People	Fraud and identity theft, reputation damage	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism
24	[126]	Fingerprint Spoofing (Gel) (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Fingerprint scanner	Manipulate Data Structures	Experiment	Medium	Technology	Service disruption, Fraud	Financial Gain	User Devices, Authentication Mechanism
25	[96]	3D Mask Facial Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Camera input (facial scan)	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Theoretical	High	People	Fraud and identity theft	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Threat Categories	Attack Point	Attack Vector	Readiness Level for Threat	Difficulty to Execute	People, Process or Technology	Impact Areas	Attack Motivation	Affected Components
26	[127]	Replay Attack (Video) (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Camera input (facial scan)	Collect and Analyse Information	Experiment	Low	People	Reputation damage, Fraud	Financial Gain, Disruption	User Devices, Authentication Mechanism
27	[94]	Fake Fingerprint (3D Print) (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Fingerprint scanner	Manipulate Data Structures	Experiment	Medium	Technology	Fraud, Legal compliance violation	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism
28	[90]	Deepfake Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Camera input (facial recognition)	Manipulate Data Structures	Theoretical	High	People	Fraud and identity theft, reputation damage	Political, Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism
29	[95]	Latent Fingerprint Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	External	Fingerprint scanner	Manipulate Data Structures	Real-life incident	Medium	Technology	Service disruption, Fraud	Financial Gain	User Devices, Authentication Mechanism
30	[80]	Phishing-driven Ransomware	External	Email (Phishing link)	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Real-life incident	Low	People	Service disruption, Finance, Reputation	Financial Gain	User Devices, Authentication Mechanism
31	[99]	Infostealer Malware (Ransomware)	External	Endpoint devices	Collect and Analyse Information	Real-life incident	Medium	Technology	Fraud, Data Theft, Financial loss	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories
32	[85]	Cloud Infrastructure Ransomware (Scattered Spider)	External	Cloud environments	Manipulate System Resources	Real-life incident	High	Process	Service disruption, Financial loss	Financial Gain, Espionage	API and Integration Points, Authentication Mechanism
33	[73]	SIM Swapping and Credential Harvesting (Ransomware)	External	Cloud identity systems	Subvert Access Control	Real-life incident	Medium	Technology	Service disruption, Fraud	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
34	[79]	Deepfake-Driven Phishing for Ransomware	External	Video calls (Impersonation)	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Experiment	High	People	Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, API Points
35	[73]	SIM Swap Attack (Identity Spoofing)	External	Mobile network (SIM card)	Subvert Access Control	Real-life incident	Medium	People	Fraud and identity theft, financial loss, reputation	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Threat Categories	Attack Point	Attack Vector	Readiness Level for Threat	Difficulty to Execute	People, Process or Technology	Impact Areas	Attack Motivation	Affected Components
36	[86]	Insider SIM Swap Attack (Identity Spoofing)	Internal	Telecom carrier employee	Abuse existing functionality	Real-life incident	Medium	Process	Legal/compliance violation, reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
37	[87]	Socially Engineering for SIM Swap (Identity Spoofing)	External	Telecom customer service	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Real-life incident	Low	People	Fraud, Identity Theft, Financial Loss	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories
38	[93]	Deepfake Audio Impersonation (Identity Spoofing)	External	Voice-based authentication	Manipulate System Resources	Real-life incident	Medium	People	Service disruption, fraud, legal compliance	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
39	[75]	Social Media Account Takeover	External	Social media platforms	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Real-life incident	Low	People	Fraud and identity theft, reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
40	[84]	Quantum Computing Attack	External	Cryptographic algorithms (e.g., RSA)	Manipulate Data Structures	Theoretical	High	Technology	Fraud and identity theft, data breaches, reputation	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories
41	[81]	Phishing Attack	External	Email (phishing link)	Engage in Deceptive Interaction	Real-life incident	Low	People	Fraud and identity theft, reputation damage, finance	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
42	[83]	MITM Attack	External	Network communication between user and server	Subvert access control	Real-life incident	High	People, Process	Service disruption, Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, API and Integration Points, User Devices
43	[93]	Brute Force Attack	External	Login page, authentication systems	Manipulate Data Structures	Real-life incident	High	Technology	Fraud and identity theft, service disruption, financial loss	Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism, User Devices
44	[82]	Session Hijacking Attack	External	Network communication	Manipulate System Resources	Real-life incident	High	People, Technology	Fraud and identity theft, service disruption	Financial Gain, Espionage	Authentication Mechanism, API, User Devices
45	[76]	Identity Federation Exploitation	External	Customer Support System	Collect and Analyse Information, Subvert Access Control	Real-life incident	Medium	Technology, People	Service disruption, Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage, Legal/compliance violation	Financial Gain, Espionage, Disruption	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories, API and Integration Points

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Threat Categories	Attack Point	Attack Vector	Readiness Level for Threat	Difficulty to Execute	People, Process or Technology	Impact Areas	Attack Motivation	Affected Components
46	[97]	Supply Chain Software Compromise	External	Third-party software, vendor access	Manipulate Data Structures, Subvert Access Control, Abuse existing Functionality	Real-life incident	High	Technology, Process, People	Service Disruption, Reputation Damage, Fraud and Identity Theft, Financial Loss	Financial Gain, Espionage, Disruption	API and Integration Points, Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories
47	[100]	Supply Chain Hardware Compromise	External	Physical supply chain of hardware components	Manipulate System Resources, Subvert Access Control	Real-life incident	High	Process, People	Service disruption, Fraud and identity theft, Reputation damage, Legal/compliance violation, Financial loss	Espionage, Disruption, Financial Gain	Authentication Mechanism, Data Repositories, User Devices

Appendix B: Threats in Focus - Countermeasures

Table A2: Table of Countermeasures

S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Countermeasure	Readiness Level for Countermeasure	Remediation Cost	Preventative and Response Measures
1	[72]	Credential Theft	Strong password policies, Multi-factor authentication, Access management, User training	Widely implemented	N/A	Detection and monitoring, Incident response, Public communication, Forensic and investigation
2	[78]	Insider Sabotage	Multi-factor authentication, access control, network monitoring	Widely implemented	N/A	Detection and monitoring, incident response, forensic and investigation
3	[74]	Credential Theft - Credential Stuffing	Multi-factor authentication, Use of CAPTCHA, Rate limiting	Widely implemented	N/A	Detection and monitoring, incident response, legal and policy response
4	[74]	Credential Theft - Password Spraying	Multi-factor authentication, Enforce strong password policies, account lockout mechanisms	Widely implemented	N/A	Detection and monitoring, incident response, legal and policy response
5	[74]	Malware and Trojan Attacks	Use of anti-virus, regular system patches, network monitoring	Widely implemented	N/A	Detection and monitoring, incident response, forensic and investigation
6	[74]	Phishing Attack	User training, email filtering, secure email gateways	Widely implemented	N/A	Public communication, incident response, forensic and investigation
7	[74]	Insider Attacks	Access control policies, Internal audit and monitoring	Widely implemented	N/A	Legal and policy response, forensic and investigation
8	[74]	Cryptojacking	Use of anti-malware tools, script blockers, and network monitoring	Widely implemented	N/A	Detection and monitoring, forensic and investigation
9	[74]	Stealing Clicks	Secure browser	N/A	N/A	Detection and monitoring, Incident response
10	[74]	Network Availability Attack	Use of firewalls, DDoS protection, and DNS security extensions	Widely implemented	High	Detection and monitoring, forensic and investigation, incident response
11	[74]	MITM Attack	Use of SSL/TLS encryption, secure certificates, VPNs	Widely implemented	Less than high	Detection and monitoring, forensic and investigation, legal and policy response
12	[74]	51% Attack	Strong consensus algorithms, network monitoring	Available	High	Legal and policy response, detection and monitoring
13	[11]	Identity-Based and Social Engineering Attacks	Multi-factor authentication, credential protection, session token management	Available	Not high (Depending on scale)	Detection and monitoring, incident response, legal and policy response
14	[11]	Cloud-Centric Attacks	Cloud-native application protection platforms (CNAPPs), cloud monitoring, runtime protection	Available (Cloud visibility tools, CNAPPs)	High	Detection and monitoring, incident response
15	[11]	Supply Chain Attacks	Vendor management, security assessments, monitoring third-party software	Available	High (Depending on the scale of the attack)	Incident response, forensic investigation, monitoring
16	[11]	Election Targeting	Strong monitoring systems, voter data protection, multi-layer security in election systems	N/A	High	Detection and monitoring, public communication, legal and policy response

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Countermeasure	Readiness Level for Countermeasure	Remediation Cost	Preventative and Response Measures
17	[102]	ARCHER supercomputer attack (Misuse of user accounts)	Renewing SSH keys and passwords, Strong Authentication (SSH key and password combination)	Widely implemented (SSH keys, strong authentication mechanisms)	Medium (requires system-wide update and enforcement)	Detection and Monitoring, Incident response, Forensic and Investigation
18	[91]	DeepFake Voice Spoofing	Embedded orthogonal and irreversible signatures, Differential Privacy	Need further research (prototypes like SecureSpectra exist)	High	Detection and Monitoring, Incident response, Legal and Policy response
19	[88]	Disclosure of Identity Data	Encryption of identity-related information	Available (encryption techniques are widely available)	N/A	Detection and Monitoring, Legal and Policy response, Public Communication
20	[123]	ID Database Compromised	Encryption, Multi-factor authentication (MFA), Monitoring for anomalies	Available (current measures like encryption and authentication are widely available)	Less than high	Detection and Monitoring, Legal and Policy response, Incident Response
21	[124]	Privileged Account Compromise	Access Management, Identity Governance and Administration	Widely implemented	High	Detection and Monitoring, Incident response, Forensic and Investigation
22	[125]	Surveillance	Encrypted communication	Widely implemented	High	Detection and Monitoring, Incident response, Legal and Policy response
23	[89]	Facial Print Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	Liveness detection, depth sensors	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Legal Response
24	[126]	Fingerprint Spoofing (Gel) (Biometric Spoofing)	Liveness detection, temperature/moisture check	Available	Medium	Incident Response, Forensic Investigation
25	[96]	3D Mask Facial Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	3D Face mapping, liveness detection	Needs further research	High	Detection and Monitoring
26	[127]	Replay Attack (Video) (Biometric Spoofing)	Liveness detection, anti-replay algorithms	Widely implemented	Medium	Forensic Investigation, Legal Response
27	[94]	Fake Fingerprint (3D Print) (Biometric Spoofing)	Liveness detection, advanced material detection	Needs further research	Medium	Detection, Incident Response
28	[90]	Deepfake Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	Liveness detection, AI-based detection tools	Needs further research	High	Public Communication, Detection
29	[95]	Latent Fingerprint Attack (Biometric Spoofing)	Liveness detection, electrical properties detection	Available	Medium	Incident Response, Forensic Investigation
30	[80]	Phishing-driven Ransomware	User awareness, MFA, email filtering	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Incident Response
31	[99]	Infostealer Malware (Ransomware)	Endpoint Detection and Response (EDR), MFA	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Forensic Investigation
32	[85]	Cloud Infrastructure Ransomware (Scattered Spider)	MFA, Cloud Access Management Tools	Available	High	Detection and Monitoring, Legal Response, Incident Response

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S.No.	Sources	Threat Name	Countermeasure	Readiness Level for Countermeasure	Remediation Cost	Preventative and Response Measures
33	[73]	SIM Swapping and Credential Harvesting (Ransomware)	MFA, Phishing prevention, Credential monitoring	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection, Legal Response, Incident Response
34	[79]	Deepfake-Driven Phishing for Ransomware	Real-time AI detection, Verification Layers	Needs further research	High	Detection and Monitoring, Legal Response, Public Communication
35	[73]	SIM Swap Attack (Identity Spoofing)	Multi-factor authentication (MFA) alternatives (e.g., Authenticator apps, hardware tokens), carrier PIN setups	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Incident response, Legal Response
36	[86]	Insider SIM Swap Attack (Identity Spoofing)	Enhanced security procedures at telecom providers, monitoring for insider threats, and employee education	Needs further research	Medium	Incident Response, Legal and Policy response
37	[87]	Socially Engineering for SIM Swap (Identity Spoofing)	Advanced identity verification protocols, use of biometric authentication for identity verification	Widely implemented	Low	Detection and Monitoring, Public Communication
38	[93]	Deepfake Audio Impersonation (Identity Spoofing)	AI-based voice liveness detection, biometric matching across multiple modalities (voice, face, etc.)	Needs further research	High	Public Communication, Incident Response
39	[75]	Social Media Account Takeover	Multi-factor authentication (MFA), regular password changes, detection of suspicious login activity	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Public Communication, Incident Response
40	[84]	Quantum Computing Attack	Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC), quantum-resistant encryption algorithms (CRYSTALS-Dilithium, FALCON)	Needs further research	High	Detection and Monitoring, Legal Response
41	[81]	Phishing Attack	Multi-factor authentication (MFA), user education, anti-phishing filters, regular software updates	Widely implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Incident Response, Legal Response
42	[83]	MITM Attack	End-to-end encryption, secure TLS configurations, mutual authentication (e.g., PACE protocol), MFA	Widely implemented	Low	Detection and Monitoring, Legal and Policy Response, Forensic Investigation
43	[93]	Brute Force Attack	Multi-factor authentication (MFA), CAPTCHA, account lockout after failed attempts, strong password policies	Widely implemented	Low	Detection and Monitoring, Incident Response, Legal Response
44	[82]	Session Hijacking Attack	End-to-end encryption (TLS), secure session management (tokens), multi-factor authentication (MFA), session expiration	Widely implemented	Low	Detection and Monitoring, Incident Response, Forensic Investigation
45	[76]	Identity Federation Exploitation	Enhanced Security Monitoring, User Training, MFA, Segmentation of Systems	Implemented	Medium	Detection and Monitoring, Incident Response, Legal and Policy Response, Forensic Investigation
46	[97]	Supply Chain Software Compromise	Vendor management, Security assessments, Software Bill of Materials (SBOM), Secure Development Life Cycle (SDLC) integration	Implemented	High	Detection and Monitoring, Legal and Policy Response, Incident Response
47	[100]	Supply Chain Hardware Compromise	Firmware integrity checks, Remote firmware management	Implemented	High	Detection and Monitoring, Incident Response, Legal and Policy Response

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